
Co-Creation Hub:

Empowering Europe's Disadvantaged Youth through Collaborative Social Entrepreneurship & Innovation

List of participants

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1. Excellence

1.1 Objectives

1.1.1 Project Summary

We must engage all of society in research and innovation processes.

— Commissioner Carlos Moedas on Science Education for Responsible Citizenship Report, 2015

Technology and globalisation are significantly shifting business in all sectors, increasing the pace of change in the necessary skills within existing jobs. On average, a third of the skillsets required to perform today's jobs will be wholly new by 2020 (WEF, 2017). There is a major need for innovative approaches to train youth for jobs that don't yet exist; this is a significant challenge in our current dynamic European Society.

Standard approaches to learning and teaching must be augmented by new programs that develop the essential overarching skills that are required by the needs of the jobs of 2020 and beyond. These include fostering innovation, creative problem-solving skills, prototyping and testing, working in diverse and creative teams, and the ability to organize and manage projects. Teaching these innovation and team skills cannot be done by rote learning; the approach must incorporate authentic opportunities for students to work with experienced creative problem solvers to address problems of high interest to them. This kind of preparatory curricula must be dynamic and responsive to evolving societal challenges and incorporate alternative learning pathways such as design thinking sessions, hackathons or sprinters, for example. New techniques, such as short courses in coding, peer-to-peer teaching, transdisciplinary project-based learning and gamification are also required. There is a need to open up education by bringing both formal and non-formal education providers, local communities and local businesses closer together by involving the private sector and civil society in education. Young people need to develop their innovation capacity by learning new highly valued skills while working together to address real societal challenges.

According to the International Labour Organization, in the European Union member states 25% of the youth (15-24 years old) are not in school, training or employment. Reducing the number in this category is a pressing challenge for the European Union. A new approach to engaging youth that allows their energy, enthusiasm, and desire for contributing and participating more fully in our society is needed. To accomplish this, we need a paradigm shift to recognise the value and importance of youth in addressing current societal challenges. This will require new partnerships and a program to teach skills that can be applied to complex problems. Now is the time to build this new capacity that will develop innovative ways of connecting youth, businesses, schools, and society, with a strong focus on the 'on-the-ground' impact for all of society. In addition to developing the skills required to meet this goal, social entrepreneurship education policies and programmes can contribute to generating jobs, and fostering innovation and poverty reduction through the empowerment of disadvantaged members of the community (UN 2011¹). We propose a program that can accomplish these goals throughout the European Union at a network of hubs that directly address the creation and use of these new skill sets.

The Co-Creation Hub Approach

To empower less privileged youth (aged 6 - 18) and their communities, Co-Creation Hub (CCHub) will train youth in a dynamic set of technological and organisational skills needed for 2020 and beyond. To achieve this, CCHub will involve stakeholders (including youth) to jointly identify, adapt and pilot most effective practices for social entrepreneurship education to develop key skills of youth, including: creativity, entrepreneurial skills, risk taking adaptability and innovation capacity, problem solving skills, skills related to effective teamwork and skills for sharing information and knowledge.

The CCHub innovation is a multi-faceted approach to equip disadvantaged youth with the social entrepreneurship skills they need to tackle their community challenges in collaboration with local stakeholders. Through the CCHub approach: 1) Disadvantaged youth are trained in skills they need for the future; 2) Youth are embedded in their local community workforce; 3) Youth are equipped to tackle European and local community challenges and 4) Communities are empowered to solve their problems collaboratively.

The Co-Creation Hub consortium partners have experience working directly with a number of youth communities in their respective countries, and as a pathway to engagement, will weave the activities of the CCHub project in with the existing programmes for young people offered by the collaborating organisations. These include programmes for: unemployed youth (IT, AT, GR), migrant background (IT, NL, GR, CZ, IE), youth arts & disability/arts & mental health (IE), high school-dropout at-risk students (RO), cultural minorities (CZ), refugee education (GR, NL), geographical disadvantaged (NL, CH), gender and LGBTQ+ (IE, NL), and intergenerational education (IE). Throughout the project, in both management and activities, gender mainstreaming will be taken into accountⁱⁱ.

CCHub will create an environment for youth to develop ventures that tackle issues that are both important for the local communities and have Pan-European applications. The project will consist of three key phases:

- **Phase I: Initiation Phase:** The project will benchmark and develop pedagogical methodologies in collaborative social entrepreneurship and innovation with disadvantaged youth. Local partners, including youth, will participate in training on key topics such as social innovation, co-creation, tinkering and making, gender equity, and business model development;
- **Phase II: Local Action:** CCHub will pilot a series of innovative social actions, co-created with disadvantaged youth, where youth will be guided in their entrepreneurial journeyⁱⁱⁱ. By developing social enterprises that tackle key community challenges, young people will collaborate with local enterprises and experts in the chosen topic, and will receive training on key social entrepreneurship and innovation skills;
- **Phase III: Broadening Impact:** The relevant results, outcomes and lessons learned in the pilot programmes throughout Europe will be consolidated in a series of toolkits and resources, and collected in the CCHub Toolkits. These will be disseminated through the CCHub Platform, Impact Hub Platforms and other relevant networks (e.g: Scientix, Ashoka, etc. - see Table 2.2), reaching thousands of teachers and schools. This will be accompanied by a series of online training materials (e.g.: MOOC in collaboration with Coursera through partnerships of P1) and innovative training sessions implemented by partners. This will enable Europe-wide impact.

The CCHub project will also provide an online platform to share and exchange activities, expertise, best practices, lessons learned and relevant opportunities at the European level. CCHub will produce resources in 10 languages (9 EU languages + Arabic). CCHub will leverage diversity as a way to enrich communities and openness as a tool to support local growth for the overall harmonious development of the European Union. Across Europe and partner countries, the CCHub network will foster capacity building, provide training for CCHub project leaders, and encourage mobility across the network.

Youth-led Community Change

In CCHub, disadvantaged youth will be actively involved as agents for change in collaboration between civil society, enterprises, research institutes and community at large through social innovation learning opportunities that apply project-based and Design Thinking principles. CCHub activities are co-guided by youth and (local) enterprises, and supported by other relevant stakeholders from the community. Young people play a prominent role in the development and implementation of all CCHub activities, and youth organisations will be represented in the management structures of the CCHub project and the activities of all CCHub partners. The CCHub project partners will collaborate closely with these stakeholders, to run innovation and social entrepreneurship-related activities for youth and families and address locally relevant

issues that link to the Horizon 2020 Grand Societal Challenges,^{iv} in a co-creation approach to problem solving. The local CCHub partners, in collaboration with local supporters, have identified preliminary topics with community relevance (see section 1.3).

Bridging Social Entrepreneurship and Education Communities across Europe

The cross-sectoral partnerships within the communities and existing partnerships will enable each CCHub partner to implement CCHub activities with less privileged youth communities, including: unemployed youth, youth with disabilities, young women, migrant, refugees, LGBTQ+ youth and geographically disadvantaged communities^v (see section 1.3 for partner networks). CCHub brings together European social entrepreneurship specialists and STEAM education communities together to co-create an innovative training programme. Youth participants will use the skills and ideas obtained through this training to create their own innovative solutions for local challenges and develop them into social enterprises. By the end of the project, CCHub will have run at least 330 community sessions, and developed new and innovative training materials in social innovation, including a MOOC for teachers and educators; serving 100 000 young people, 4000 teachers, and 4000 private and public sector representatives in 11 countries. CCHub will also establish 100 long-lasting youth-industry-civil society partnerships.

Overall, the main vision of CCHub is to inspire, empower and engage disadvantaged youth to foster their entrepreneurial attitude and affect social change in their communities using sustainable, inclusive and innovative approaches.

1.1.2 Project Objectives

To empower youth with social innovation-related skills, CCHub will co-create, pilot, evaluate and scale-up an innovative social entrepreneurship programme for Europe's less privileged future innovators. In a nutshell, CCHub will identify and support best practices for social entrepreneurship and innovation learning and teaching and create an encouraging environment for youth, schools and communities to use social entrepreneurship and innovation training to tackle community issues that are both important for the local communities and have pan-European applications. CCHub will pilot training programmes with different groups of disadvantaged youth in 9 European countries. CCHub will provide a framework to guide youth's entrepreneurial journey through a series of MOOCs, as well as an open source implementation guide for resource-challenged communities. The CCHub Toolkits include activities, plans and professional development guides for educators to support the development of Social Entrepreneurship & Innovation education initiatives across Europe, as well as academic research that will inform policy and practice. The CCHub main objectives are:

O1. Equip disadvantaged youth with skills that increase employability and competitiveness through collaborative social entrepreneurship and innovation training.

Through existing education and youth networks, youth (ages 6 - 18) will be engaged to co-create and follow a participatory training and development programme focused on social entrepreneurship and innovation. This training includes a guided design-thinking process, and training on entrepreneurship, innovation, empathy, prototyping and making, storytelling, and leadership, provided by the CCHub consortium, in collaboration with relevant local partners. Where appropriate, and especially among younger innovators, the focus will be placed on developing creativity, innovation, critical thinking, empathy, problem-solving and making skills, through applied STEAM (Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics) and Maker education activities. In addition, older students will engage activities focused on business model development, gender-related challenges, networking, communication and evaluation. An overview of CCHub skills and related activities and training workshops is provided in Table 1.3a.

By targeting less privileged youth specifically, CCHub will contribute to building more inclusive societies and giving opportunities to all. Each partner will co-create and pilot the CCHub project with disadvantaged youth communities in their network (see section 1.3), resulting in tested, adapted and improved resources for general use as well as recommendations for use with specific youth communities. CCHub will support youth in developing both the hard and soft skills required to explore new markets and create business models, to ultimately increase youth's employability and competitiveness. Equipped with the tools to engage in society, youth can create their own opportunities that have social impact. CCHub activities in collaboration with local enterprises will ensure that youth are embedded in local business practices and expand their professional network, creating strong connections with the local workforce in view of future jobs.

O2. Empower youth to create social ventures that tackle local community challenges.

In the CCHub project, European social innovation and entrepreneurship specialists, STEAM education networks and youth and their communities come together to co-create an innovative training programme. The programme will guide youth (in collaboration with educators, enterprises, civil society, and local government) to identify local challenges that matter to them and to their communities, using the Design Thinking methodology. Youth participants will form project groups around these challenges and, supported by the project and local enterprises, develop relevant skills (see O1). Youth participants will use the skills and ideas obtained through this training to create their own innovative solutions for local challenges and develop them into social enterprises. To achieve this, CCHub will guide young people in their social

entrepreneurial journey and provide youth with relevant local mentorship, building on P5-ASH and P3-IH-IT international expertise with social innovation training for youth and youth mentorship.

CCHub focuses on engaging young people as drivers of social change, rather than as an audience to change. Youth will be actively involved in the design, implementation and evaluation phases of the project. Special attention will be dedicated to gender-sensitive design throughout the CCHub project and all individual youth projects, as well as to the encouragement of youth projects developed specifically to address gender-issues.

Each CCHub partner has established partnerships with a variety of community agents, including enterprises, civil society associations, representatives of the social and service economy, and research institutes (listed in Section 2.2.2). Through these partnerships, professionals from the local community will be involved in bringing real-life projects to youth groups and schools, and guide them to identify and tackle real community issues. Ultimately, CCHub will empower youth to lead collaborative actions for community change.

O3. Provide tools, resources and environment for improved learning and teaching of innovation-related skills in formal, informal and non-formal education in Europe, as well as online.

CCHub will co-create, pilot and evaluate learning and teaching activities in social entrepreneurship and innovation-related skills for youth ages 6 - 18. These evaluated activities will be collated into CCHub Toolkits: collections of tools and resources for both educators and youth. CCHub will provide an open, accessible and encouraging environment to support experimentation and disseminate the CCHub approaches and models for teaching and learning skills through project-based social entrepreneurship and innovation training.

CCHub will combine the evaluations from each pilot location by demographic group and societal challenge addressed (e.g. best practices for inner-city teenagers, for migrant teenagers, or girls in rural areas, including location specific challenges). These results will be synthesized into social entrepreneurship & innovation teaching tools and resources and collected in the CCHub Toolkits, accompanied by a MOOC developed by P1-UL through Leiden University's partnership with Coursera. This MOOC will contain pedagogical guidelines for implementing the pilot in a range of formats and with a variety of (youth) target groups. The resources, based on pilot evaluations, will be linked to complementary case study videos and interviews from the pilots in a modular manner, enabling users to access both the entire course and supporting resources, as well as individual elements related to specific learning outcomes, skills, community challenges and target groups.

A CCHub Platform will be developed to host all material developed by CCHub online, and make it freely available for use for the CCHub network and beyond. The CCHub platform will be based on web frameworks developed by P1-UL, that support easy localisation of local websites and exploit resources from existing European projects (like EU Space Awareness). The platform will provide resources for the CCHub online community of practice for discussion and support, and will function as a forum and repository for new social innovation projects. A suitable youth platform within the CCHub web platform will be co-developed in collaboration with the Advisory Board (which includes youth members).

O4. Strengthen networks for collaboration among formal, non-formal, and informal education providers, enterprises, research institutes, civil society and the social and service economy, to foster intergenerational and lifelong learning.

To build local capacity around social entrepreneurship and leverage new partnerships, all CCHub partners will participate in a training workshop on effective tools for community building, co-creation, and social entrepreneurship and innovation in the first year of the project. The training workshop will foster peer-to-peer learning, whereby participants can learn from each other's former experiences and previous projects, and will engage participants (including youth) in co-creating CCHub the pilot programme.

Co-creation with key community stakeholders builds on local capacity, ensures the project meets community needs, provides community members with ownership of the project, and supports the sustainability and legacy of the CCHubs. This also ensures that participants (including youth) are engaged in risk-taking and problem solving activities from initial participation in the CCHub project, and promotes intergenerational and lifelong learning. CCHub will foster expertise sharing and networking by implementing the pilot programme through events that bring together youth, education professionals, researchers, representatives of local enterprises, other innovators, the social and service economy, and key actors within the community. A full list of stakeholders is presented in section 4, Table 4.1a.

CCHub local programmes and content will be established in a participatory, community-driven development process to meet local needs. All CCHub partners will localise, co-develop and implement activities with relevant stakeholders using co-development guidelines provided through WP3 and WP4 of the CCHub project. Whenever possible, school management boards, school heads, teachers, and/or parents associations will also be invited to co-create and participate in CCHub activities.

O5. Empower the broader relevant local, national, and international education communities through CCHub methodologies, resources, and approaches.

By combining European STEAM education and social entrepreneurship and innovation networks, and providing the learning opportunities and resources through partners' extensive networks, CCHub will empower the broadest possible European education community with CCHub resources. The CCHub community and other educators will use the digital CCHub platform to share and exchange activities, best practices, lessons learned, and relevant opportunities. To ensure the legacy and reach of the project, all CCHub resources will be shared on existing large online educational repositories, including the Scientix platform. Moreover, localised CCHub resources will be shared and promoted through relevant national networks and repositories, to reach out to thousands of schools and learning sites across Europe. Research produced by CCHub will be shared through peer-reviewed, open access publications. To facilitate adaptation and maximise impact in Europe and beyond, all CCHub products will be fully based on Open Standards and will follow the guidelines on open access for scientific publications and research data in Horizon 2020. All resources will be produced using a Creative Commons License.

Each CCHub will also organise teacher continuing professional development workshops at national and regional teacher events to empower educators to use the CCHub resources. During the last phase of the project, a final CCHub Showcase will be organised at the Ars Electronica festival as part of the U19 Ars Electronica Prix, to bring together partners, selected students and teachers, and key stakeholders, to consolidate the outcomes of the project, share best practices and discuss the sustainability and legacy of CCHub.

O6. Establish partnerships with the private sector and develop a sustainability plan that goes beyond the duration of the project.

To ensure the sustainability of the CCHub project, each partner will build a sound sustainability strategy in collaboration with local organisations and government. Work will begin in the first steps of the project:

while co-creating the pilot and community projects to be implemented in each partner country, a business model and an income generating model will be designed. Each CCHub partner will be supported to develop a sustainable financial plan (as per WP6) in collaboration with local partners. Where present, the regional Impact Hub (facilitated through P3-IH-IT) will support the local CCHub. In addition, local partners will explore the possibility of supporting initiatives to establish additional CCHub programmes in their countries.

Facilitated by community ownership over the CCHub project, each CCHub partner will work with the relevant governments (local, regional, or national) to ensure local support throughout the project and sustainability beyond the closure of this project. CCHub will encourage the private sector to support schools (for example by exploring the possibility to expand the tax benefits for companies that support culture and arts to also support social entrepreneurship and innovation training for youth, or to encourage companies to include this as part of their Corporate Social Responsibility). Local CCHub programmes will also lobby to influence policy and practice and lobby for government-supported engagement between schools and industry at local and/or regional levels and work closely with school governance to incorporate social entrepreneurship and innovation into schools’ activities. Both government and school governance will be involved in CCHub at all levels.

1.2 Relation to the work programme

The scope of the work programme call *Education and skills: empowering Europe’s young innovators* is diverse, broad and ambitious. As an Innovation Action, CCHub will address the challenge and scope mentioned in the *Europe in a changing world – inclusive, innovative and reflective Societies* work programme through the accompanying measures, and will satisfy all the objectives of the call within the available time and funding by an innovative solutions outlined in Table 1.2a.

Table 1.2a. Key challenges and scope identified by the call and respective CCHub Solutions and Outputs.

Key challenges identified by the call	CCHub Solutions
<i>(1) Creativity, entrepreneurial skills, risk taking adaptability and innovation capacity, problem solving skills, skills related to effective teamwork and sharing information and knowledge, may all be key competitive advantages for Europeans, starting from young children.</i>	CCHub provides a framework to empower youth through collaborative social innovation, by connecting them with their local communities and tackling real local societal challenges. This will be achieved by project-based learning. In this way young people will work in teams to learn and experience a diverse set of skills, including creativity, entrepreneurial skills, risk taking adaptability, social innovation and problem solving skills.
<i>(2) [...] schools and educational institutions, as well as non-formal ways of learning, empower Europe’s young innovators with the skills they need from early on in life [...]</i>	CCHub will develop pedagogical guidelines based on the implementation of the social innovation programme/pilot with local youth communities. The pedagogical guidelines will be part of an innovative curriculum to be delivered as MOOCs for teachers and educators

<p><i>(3) Empowering the young [...] is particularly important to building more inclusive societies giving opportunities to all, including young innovators from less privileged backgrounds or those with disabilities in order to address inequalities.</i></p>	<p>CCHub will specifically target youth from less privileged backgrounds, including marginalised groups and those with disabilities. CCHub will emphasize the importance of promoting gender equality in all CCHub activities and actions.</p> <p>CCHub will empower youth to address social challenges (including inequalities) by developing social enterprises that tackle these issues.</p>
<p><i>(4) [...] to improve learning and teaching in innovation-related skills for young boys and girls at the age of primary and secondary education through the design and piloting of new innovative ways of skills education, including technologies, processes and relations.</i></p>	<p>CCHub will design and pilot innovative skills teaching and learning methods in collaboration with youth (of primary and secondary school age), teachers and educators, local enterprises and civil society. This will be achieved by new relations between social innovation and STEAM communities, use of youth trends in technology to teach social entrepreneurship (e.g.: coderdojo) and community and youth-driven processes.</p>
<p>Specific Scope Identified by the call</p>	<p>CCHub Actions</p>
<p><i>1) New approaches for educating skills need to developed, piloted and scaled up</i></p>	<p>CCHub will co-develop, a participatory innovation and social entrepreneurship training with relevant stakeholders (including youth themselves). Through a facilitated process, CCHub will pilot co-create a curriculum for social innovation targeted at disadvantaged youth. This training will be adapted, piloted and evaluated with 11 groups in 9 countries.</p>
<p><i>2) lack of sufficient collaboration with entrepreneurial stakeholders in teaching and students practice and a lack of inter-generational learning</i></p>	<p>CCHub will engage local enterprises and civil society organisations in the development of the social innovation programme in a co-creation approach to education. Enterprises will also be involved in providing entrepreneurship and innovation skills training for youth, in close collaboration with formal, non-formal, and informal education providers, enterprises, research institutes, and civil society.</p> <p>Participants of community co-creation processes and trainings will include youth, as well as civil society members, local enterprises, researchers, among other groups.</p>
<p><i>3) Young people need to be supported with tools, resources and an open environment, encouraging experimentation and the development of joint projects including based on interdisciplinary approaches</i></p>	<p>CCHub will empower youth to use resources and tools provided by the project partners within the open encouraging environment of their own community to address problems or issues relevant to them, in collaboration with local enterprises. The project partners and diverse community groups, as well as the modules in STEAM making and tinkering, social innovation and social sciences/humanities offered in conjunction with the project development, mean that the participants will have skills across a range of disciplines that they can apply to their social innovation project.</p>

<p><i>4) Effective supporting schemes should guide young people into their entrepreneurial journey</i></p>	<p>The CCHub pilots will consist of at least 12 meetings over the course of a year, in which students will be supported by local facilitators, as well as mentors from relevant stakeholder groups, including local ImpactHubs, universities, enterprises and other society groups.</p>
<p><i>5) Building on existing initiatives in Europe, the consortia shall develop new approaches and innovative models for skills education targeted at young people</i></p>	<p>CCHub will use the expertise of consortium partners in science education (P1-UL, P2-TCD) and social entrepreneurship (P3-IH-IT and P5-ASH) and build on numerous existing research results and initiatives in Europe (see section 1.3.2 for an extensive overview of related projects of the consortium and beyond).</p>
<p><i>6) The involvement of young people in the activities of the consortium (not just as recipients of the outputs) is essential</i></p>	<p>Young people will be actively involved in the development of the CCHub Social Innovation curriculum (as co-creators). The CCHub Project Board will consist of members appointed by CCHub partners: each partner will appoint 1 representative of youth communities or organisations to serve on the Advisory Board.</p>
<p><i>7) This may include new interactive methods and new pedagogical modules that will be easily accessible and part of an open platform which will aim to reach out to thousands of schools and learning sites across Europe</i></p>	<p>CCHub will develop interactive pedagogical methods and guidelines based on the implementation of the social innovation programme/pilot with local youth communities. The guidelines will be part of an innovative curriculum to be delivered as MOOCs for teachers and educators, which will be published on an open CCHub platform, on existing education repositories and through education networks.</p>
<p><i>8) The innovative schemes and new modules will enable the young, future innovators to develop new capabilities and experimentation attitudes and turn their ideas into successful entrepreneurial and social projects</i></p>	<p>During the pilot phase, the co-creation of projects which aim to have societal impact, will be developed over the course of 12 months as young people participate in a series of training modules in topics such as making and tinkering, design thinking, social entrepreneurship, business model development, team-building and leadership skills development, and use all of these skills to create a final social project, with the potential to become a successful enterprise.</p>
<p><i>9) Promising new models combining technologies with organisational change and building new participatory relations in learning processes can be tested and adapted in different regions</i></p>	<p>CCHub pilots will be implemented, tested and adapted with different youth groups in different regions and communities in 9 countries. These pilots will bring different organisations together and start new educational relations in local and European communities in the field of Social Entrepreneurship.</p>
<p><i>10) The innovative models shall be piloted through the schools and/or other businesses and communities</i></p>	<p>The co-developed models will be piloted with a variety of youth groups, through schools, businesses, non-for-profit organisations and other community partners of the consortium. Through CCHub partnerships, professionals from local communities will bring community-relevant knowledge and practices to the design-thinking projects.</p>

<p>11)...[] providing young people with a practical set of creative and entrepreneurial skills</p>	<p>The CCHub pilots, MOOCs and CCHub Platform will provide young people with extensive training and practical experience in a diverse set of skills related with social entrepreneurship, including skills in creativity, and innovation, and entrepreneurial skills such as business model development and problem solving.</p>
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1.3 Concept and methodology

CCHub is based on robust, established and proofed concepts stemming from education research, community development theory and practice, and national and European policies. The CCHub project will have specific outcomes, such as providing accessible innovation and social entrepreneurship-related activities, developing innovation and entrepreneurship skills and preparing the next generation for the workforce. However, the most salient benefit from the CCHub project will be using social innovation training to support (young) people to “realise their capacity to shape the designed dimensions of their local worlds - that they have the inclination, motivation and wherewithal to effect change” (Ryan et al., 2016). According to the report *Unequal Nation*^{vi}, social innovations “aim to transform social relations by equalising access to power and resources. As such, social innovations can empower specific groups of people and challenge unequal distribution across society.” The overall CCHub concepts demonstrate the need for and effectiveness of the approach, as well as the quality of the selected methodology.

Fig 1.3. Co-Creation Hub approach. *In the Initiation Phase, the project will benchmark and co-develop pedagogical methodologies and provide training; In Phase II Local Action, CCHub will pilot a series of innovative social actions, co-created with disadvantaged youth. This is a central phase of the project, where*

new approaches will be piloted, tested and adapted. In Phase III Broadening Impact, the relevant results of phases I and II will be consolidated in a series of toolkits and resources. These will be disseminated through relevant networks (e.g: Scientix, Ashoka, etc. - see Table 2.2) this will be accompanied by a series of online training materials (e.g.: MOOCs) and innovative training sessions implemented by partners, serving at least 10 000 young people and educators across Europe.

CCHub will work directly with the communities who will use the CCHub programmes to identify the issues relevant to them, and will then draw together other local stakeholders to develop a strategy to address these issues through the core activities of the CCHub, involving all actors and allowing each group to influence the development process. Gender equality, and other forms of inclusivity, can be highlighted by the diversity of the participants involved in the development process, as much as in the choice of researchers or business people to work with, for example.

1.3.1 Overall Concepts Underpinning Co-Creation Hub Less Privileged Youth Communities

Disadvantaged youth is an umbrella term which embraces all young people with fewer opportunities than their peers and in some countries other terms like youth-at-risk, vulnerable youth, disconnected youth or socially excluded youth are preferred to describe social inequality among young people (Bendit & Stokes, 2003). CCHub will be working with the following disadvantaged youth communities in Europe:

Unemployed Youth: Due to the 2009 recession in Europe, only 15 per cent of young men and 10 per cent of young women between ages 16–19 are employed full-time^{vii}. When taking into consideration the need to foster competitiveness through innovation and creativity, recent studies have advocated for entrepreneurship as a viable a solution to youth unemployment. With the right structure and facilitated administrative processes, young people can create enterprises as means to find and create new jobs^{viii}. Target group engaged through existing collaborations with P3 - IH-IT, P6-AE, P9-IH-RO, P10-IH-HU and P11-IH-GR.

Youth with disabilities: In the EU, presumably, people with disabilities are the largest social minority – about 80 million Europeans have a disability^{ix}. There are no reliable statistics on the number of youth with disabilities in Europe^x, partly because (1) youth with disabilities as a group are not quite visible on the policy and research agenda, and (2) overall disability statistics varies accordingly to the different understanding of a disability across the states. In CCHub, a youth disability group is engaged through existing collaborations between Trinity Centre for People with Disabilities with P2-TCD.

Young women: An EU Advisory Group on gender report^{xi} states that “in collaborative and creative economies, gender is a decisive factor explaining inequalities and potential restrictions to growth.” Women’s labor is more likely than men’s to be underpaid or unpaid, and in Europe 9.6% of young women are unemployed compared with 9.3% of young men^{xii}. The Gender Futures group^{xiii} finds that “the goals of social innovation simply will not be achieved without acknowledging and addressing the presence and impact of gender inequality.” In addition, there is a lack of overlap between the gender equality movement and the social innovation movement. CCHub will address gender inequality awareness and reflection as a core part of the training for all participating young people. P2-TCD will work with Young Women in Technology students to develop social innovations addressing gendered inequalities. For additional gender considerations in CCHub, see section 1.3.3.

Migrant & Refugee youth: Students with a migrant background tend to have lower educational outcomes than their peers in most OECD countries^{xiv}. Across Europe, young people from a migrant background are twice as likely to leave school early without qualifications. The growing proportion of students with a migrant background requires adaptation of the school systems to deliver high quality education for all and to capitalise on the potential of this diversity^{xv}. CCHub engages this group through existing collaborations with P1-UL, P2-TCD, P3-IH-IT, P7-MB, P11-IH-GR.

Geographically disadvantaged youth communities: Rural areas represent more than 90% of EU territory and contain more than half of the EU's population. Some EU rural areas face particular challenges as regards growth, jobs and sustainability in the coming years. According to Erasmus+ project Salto Youth^{xvi}, young people in these rural areas often face a series of challenges related to education and employment opportunities. CCHub will work directly with geographically disadvantaged youth communities, namely through P1-UL and P3-IH-IT.

Cultural Minority Youth Communities: Mounting evidence has been accumulated about the disadvantages in educational performance and advancement that young people from ethnic minority backgrounds face across Europe^{xvii}. Ethnically differentiated educational practices are crucial determinants of social inclusion. In Europe's case, these educational differences are forging inequalities that challenge the European Union's fundamental values and chip away at the foundations of social order. CCHub engages this group through existing collaborations with P1-UL, P2-TCD, P3-IH-IT, P7-MB, P11-IH-GR.

LGBTQ+: Included in the United Nations Human Rights Council list of "at-risk" peoples are lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer and intersex people (LGBTQ+). The Young Foundation mentions ongoing bullying and discrimination on the grounds of gender identity and sexual orientation, with 65% of LGBTQ+ youth experiencing bullying and harassment. This social group is also shows lower school completion levels and are frequently at risk of violence. CCHub will work with LGBTQ+ youth groups in at least one partner country (P2-TCD with BeLonGTo in Ireland).

Changemaker Schools (CS): CCHub will also work with schools which actively foster empathy, leadership, teamwork and creativity; 'changemaking skills'. There are 12 CS in Ireland and over 200 globally. These schools are pioneering in their approaches to systemic change in education and equipping children with 21st century skills. CS implement a curriculum which encompasses 'changemaking skills' and the skills of the 21st century within the current school curriculum. Changemaker Schools have identified a need for a programme that explores social innovation in response to social problems and will collaborate with CCHub to implement the CCHub pilot programme in CS, through P2 - TCD and P5 - ASH.

Social Innovation & Social Entrepreneurship

Social innovation is central to the European Horizon 2020 goals relating to 'smart, sustainable and inclusive growth'. There are several key EU objectives to which CCHub seeks to contribute: promoting social innovation as a source of growth and jobs; sharing information about social innovation in Europe; and supporting innovative entrepreneurs and mobilising investors and public organisations. This strategic focus underlines the importance and urgency of the research-action-training exercise promoted by the project.

In the European Union political discourse, social innovation has been applied since the early 1990s to indicate a new approach to tackle local development in a larger anti-poverty policy framework to become, today, a key component in the European Commission strategy for economic competitive growth and social cohesion. Scholars have observed the development of a new 'social innovation paradigm' since the turn of the 21st century (Nicholls and Murdock, 2012). The general argument within much business management-oriented literature is that 'wicked problems' such as climate change, migration, and demographic challenges posed by an ageing population, cannot be addressed by 'bureaucratic' governments or 'inefficient' charities (Yunus, 2009). Instead, it is argued, we should look to business and civil society to develop new solutions to social problems, which are more effective, efficient, sustainable, and/or socially just than existing solutions (Phills et al. 2008).

Until recently, in the literature the evolution and expansion of social entrepreneurship is mostly discussed in economic terms, using economic models of growth (Achleitner et al., 2009, Weber et al., 2012, Thompson and MacMillan, 2010, Drayton and Budinich, 2010). Thereby, the models turn a blind eye to the embeddedness of social entrepreneurship as a social phenomenon that operates within social relations (cf. Granovetter, 1985). This is the starting point for the proposed project. Recently projects have conducted

internationally comparative research on the topic (e.g. EFSEIIS, SEFORIS, and more). The outputs and resources from these (European) projects will be leveraged to contribute to the (co-)development of the CCHub project, the engagement of stakeholders and implementation of activities. Section 1.3.2 provides an overview of these projects.

Research has only just begun to unpack the extent to which social innovation is influenced by the nature of the relationships between the state, market and civil society (Moulaert, 2009), which we know can vary considerably across different countries, regions, and (particularly) welfare regimes. The fact that CCHub will have a variety of partners from different countries involved in this project will allow us to study and understand this variety and its relevance. It is broadly accepted that social innovation flourishes when different groups can collaborate in the development of ideas and solutions in a supportive environment. One such model of supportive environment is offered by 'social innovation hubs', which aim to offer a thinking space that promotes grassroots entrepreneurship and innovation (Steiner and Teasdale, 2016). CCHub promotes such a model whereby individual programmes for youth are tailored to the unique local circumstances of the communities they serve.

Project Based and Collaborative Learning

Project based learning, and specially skills education, is particularly useful to developing socially innovative and transformative ideas because it moves beyond passively learning facts and reciting them out of context to prepare people for the contemporary challenges of everyday 21st century life. Solving highly complex problems requires that people are able to draw upon a firm platform of fundamental skills, but also a range of 21st century skills such as teamwork, problem solving, research gathering, time management, information synthesising and utilising technological innovation. With this combination of skills, people become directors of their learning process, particularly if they are guided and mentored properly and in a context which facilitates learning outcomes successfully. Another key aspect of education and learning is the environment in which it takes place (Strange and Banning, 2001). The framework for a successful professional learning community outlined by DuFour and DuFour (2010), entails focusing on learning rather than teaching, working collaboratively, and being results-driven. Education is particularly important for disadvantaged communities and innovation is needed in this area (Gutiérrez, 2008). Rural schools can have a significant impact on communities when students are provided with meaningful opportunities to engage in community-based learning (Miller, 1995). All CCHub pilots will be implemented with youth from disadvantaged groups to tackle key community challenges. Specific local societal challenges have been identified in the CCHub communities to guide local CCHub activities. Preliminary topics include: energy, social inclusion, mobility, childhood obesity, wildfire control and prevention, and waste management. These challenges are aligned with the Horizon 2020 Grand Societal Challenges, namely, health; sustainable agriculture, fishery and forestry; clean and efficient energy; smart, green and integrated transport; climate action; environment, and inclusive, innovative and reflective societies.

Skills for the Future Workforce

As mentioned earlier, a range of 21st century skills are required to enable people to deal with social problems creatively and co-create a better future for themselves and for their families and communities. These types of skills include: creativity, entrepreneurial skills, risk taking adaptability and innovation capacity, problem solving skills, skills related to effective teamwork and sharing information and knowledge, empathy. When the focus goes to the skills needed for the future workforce, most of the emphasis in the current debate goes to a new way of integrating labour forces into the labour market, emphasising flexibility (or precariousness) and self entrepreneurship attitudes (or increased competition) as important skills to be empowered. Recent research carried out under the 7th Framework Programme (EFSEIIS 2017) emphasises the human dimension of social enterprises as crucial. Among social entrepreneurs, which included enterprises founded in the last decade, the average age of founders is around 42 years. The female component of founders is well represented, averaging around 50%, a much higher

percentage compared to the founders of both conventional businesses and social enterprises as well as organizations of earlier constitution.

Design Thinking and Maker Education for Social Entrepreneurship

Design Thinking (Wagner, 2012; Crichton and Carter, 2015), a problem-solving approach to learning that involves human-centred design in tackling real-world problems, through research, empathy, creativity, prototyping and re-iteration. Design Thinking is a process by which participants can tinker and talk purposefully within groups and consider, discuss, research, and explore options, and allows makers to “creatively attack the world’s greatest problems and meet people’s most urgent needs” (Hatch, 2014). CCHub will use the methodologies of Design Thinking to steer its community participatory workshops, where local stakeholders will collaborate to tackle real community challenges.

Martin (2015) outlines three crucial elements of the Maker Education that are linked to Social Entrepreneurship skills: 1) digital tools, including rapid prototyping tools and low-cost microcontroller platforms, that characterize many making projects; 2) community infrastructure, including online resources and in-person spaces and events; and 3) the maker mindset, aesthetic principles, and habits of mind that are commonplace within the community. The CCHub will provide all three of these elements. There are a number of already-established professional development tools which the CCHub network will disseminate to educators to support the uptake of maker-based learning in the vicinity of the local CCHub - these include Tinkering EU’s practitioner’s guide^{xviii}, Tinkering Studio’s MOOC^{xix}, the Curriculum Guide (Roffey et al, 2016) from Makerspace for Education and the Design Thinking Educator Resources of the “Agency By Design” project^{xx}. Consortium members and all selected youth organisations/groups will be trained to use maker education approaches and methodologies in social entrepreneurship activities.

CCHub will provide a variety of workshops and activities to develop entrepreneurship & innovation-related and 21st Century Skills, according to the theory described above. Table 1.3a gives an overview of examples developed by consortium partners and other international education projects.

Table 1.3a. Overview of potential workshops and activities that will be provided by CCHubs.

Relevant Entrepreneurship Skills	Potential CCHub activities
<i>Entrepreneurialism, perseverance, adaptability:</i> Long and short-term goals and plan to achieve these; Persist to optimise strategies or solutions; View failure as an opportunity to learn.	<i>Business model canvas activity:</i> Using the lean startup method to develop a visual plan that describes a venture’s value proposition, beneficiaries, and finances. <i>Eco-tourism experience:</i> Design, test and adapt an activity to help the economy and protect the environment and community.
<i>Creativity, curiosity, innovation:</i> Use idea creation techniques; Develop strategies or outcomes; Understand and experience real world limits; Come up with new solutions.	<i>School Redesign project:</i> A Maker challenge on a community problem posed to school groups, starting with inquiry and building on prior learning. <i>Disruption thinking exercises:</i> Including humour or unlikely scenarios into existing solutions to playfully expand ideas for innovation.
<i>Critical thinking, problem solving:</i> Define problems, explore solutions or methods to find solutions; Elaborate, refine, analyse, test and evaluate ideas; Link to prior knowledge; Use new learnings from explorations.	<i>Problem Tree:</i> Learning to identify root causes and effects of problems. <i>Paper prototyping:</i> creating drawings or models of solutions to be rapidly simulated and tested. <i>Community pilots:</i> Designing and implementing controlled experiments with target audiences based on proposed projects.

<p><i>Communication, presenting, listening:</i> Develop, implement and communicate new ideas to others effectively; Public speaking; Be open and responsive to new and diverse ideas.</p>	<p><i>Rocket Pitch Competition:</i> training for elevator pitches of projects; <i>Media production:</i> Stop Motion video workshops, audio recording workshops; <i>Community sourced communication:</i> CCHub participants write updates and create videos of their work, for the CCHub Platform.</p>
<p><i>Teamwork, collaboration:</i> Develop the ability to work in teams, use networking skills; demonstrate empathy in working with others; co-creating knowledge.</p>	<p><i>City Planning:</i> Build models of buildings in your town, improve, rebuild and review peer plans. <i>Teamwork activities:</i> Teams build halves of a bridge separately. <i>Family science activities:</i> STEAM projects that require family collaboration.</p>
<p><i>Empathy, global awareness, community participation:</i> Understand global issues; Respect and appreciate other cultures; Learn from and work collaboratively with diverse individuals in a spirit of mutual respect; Participate in local community and empathise with community members.</p>	<p><i>Design Thinking sessions:</i> Collaboratively identify relevant community issues; <i>Earth Ball activity:</i> Exploring a planet without country borders. <i>Community empathy activity:</i> What do elderly people need? Interview or shadow senior citizens to design something to help them in their everyday life. <i>Crossing the line:</i> building diversity awareness within a group. <i>Dialogue activities:</i> Open Space Technology on relevant issues for the community.</p>

As described above, social entrepreneurship and innovation training that targets and empowers youth is challenging and complex endeavour that leverages well-established concepts and methodologies. The consortium brings together the expertise in all abovementioned fields and the networks necessary for the successful implementation and scaling of the CCHub project to achieve the broadest European impact.

1.3.2 Building on European Research and Innovation activities and projects

CCHub will establish several connections and links with other relevant European Research and Innovation activities and projects. The outputs and resources from these will contribute to the development of the project, the engagement of their stakeholders and implementation of their activities. In its research, development and innovation process, CCHub will make use of the data provided by several projects. CCHub will also build on a number of projects of consortium partners.

EU Research and Innovation projects that will feed into CCHub

- BENISI FP7: Produced a toolkit to support scaling of social innovation, that will be used to evaluate how CCHub can become financially sustainable beyond the project at local level and as a European network. CCHub partner: P3 & P9.
- FP7 SEFORIS: Examines social enterprise as force for more inclusive and innovative Societies.
- FP7 EFESIIS: Analyses the eco-system of social entrepreneurship for innovative and inclusive societies.
- FP7 SELUSI: Aims to understand the market- and organization-level behaviours of social enterprises across Europe using empirical, theoretical and experimental methodologies.
- FP7 CRESSI: Explores the economic underpinnings of social innovation.
- FP7 IMPROVE: Researches social innovation in the context of macro-level policies to reduce poverty and achieve social cohesion
- FP7 TEPSIE: Explores barriers, structures and financial resources and returns around social innovation.
- FP7 SI-DRIVE: Determines the nature, characteristics and impacts of social innovation

- InnoSi: Aims on the role of innovative social investment for strengthening communities in Europe.
- FP7 EDUMIGROM: Studied how ethnic differences in education contribute to the diverging prospects for minority ethnic youth and their peers in urban settings. The findings of this project will be used to advise the implementation of CCHub.
- EU ET2020: A forum for exchanges of best practices, mutual learning, gathering and dissemination of information and evidence on among other things, enhancing creativity, innovation, and entrepreneurship, at all levels of education.
- RRI Tools: CCHub partners will act as RRI Tools trainers for partners in the CCHub network. CCHub resources will be uploaded to the RRI Tools Toolkit, and CCHub network members will be part of the RRI Tools community of practice. CCHub partner involved: P2.

Relevant consortium projects that will feed into CCHub

- ASHOKA Youth Venture: Designs experiential youth engagements that insert changemaking into the cultures of companies, schools and universities, and youth organizations. Youth Venture works with young people and partners to co-create tools and programs that help young people self-identify as changemakers and master critical pathways for thriving as changemakers, such as: empathy, collaborative leadership, and changemaking. CCHub partner involved: P5.
- ASHOKA Changemaker Schools: Enables all students to become changemakers. Students learn the essential skills of empathy, creativity, leadership, and teamwork so that they can thrive in the modern world and find solutions to our most complex problems. CCHub partner involved: P5.
- ChangemakerXChange: The global collaboration platform for young social entrepreneurs changemakers at summits around the world for exchange and co-creation of ideas. The platform brings together young social entrepreneurs from 55 different countries in Europe and beyond. CCHub partner: P5.
- Erasmus+ Salto Youth: Support, Advanced Learning and Training Opportunities for Youth, works within the Erasmus+ Youth programme, for education, training, youth and sport. CCHub will be working with SALTO-YOUTH Inclusion, Cultural Diversity and Training Resources Centres.
- Erasmus+ Tinkering EU: implements tinkering as an innovative pedagogy at European level. Tinkering EU will provide training for CCHub partners and stakeholders at the CCHub Kickoff Event. CCHub partner: P1 & P2.
- FP7 EU Universe Awareness: CCHub will engage the large network of STEAM educators (in 62 countries) established by the project to promote the use of CCHub resources and outputs. CCHub will use award winning educational activities and toolkits. CCHub partner involved: P1.
- FP7 TEMI: CCHub will use the IBSE approach and innovations to train CCHub managers and facilitators on the IBSE skills to run STEAM activities. CCHub will exploit the teachers networks to promote the use of CCHub resources and outputs. CCHub partner involved: P1 & P4.
- H2020 LIGHT2015: CCHub will use the citizen-science expertise, skills and technologies developed during the project to foster the use of citizen-science approaches in real and local issues. CCHub partner involved: P1.
- H2020 EU Space Awareness: CCHub will engage the large network of STEAM educators (23 dissemination nodes) established by Space Awareness to promote the use of CCHub resources. CCHub partner involved: P1.
- H2020 DITOs: DITOs aims to increase public participation in scientific research and innovation across Europe. CCHub will partner with DITOs to run Citizen Science projects which are locally relevant and/or involve Making skills. CCHub partner involved: P2.
- FEAST: Aims at enhancing the role that adults play when they support their children's engagement with science and technology. CCHub will use the resources produced to engage parents and carers in their child's education. CCHub partner involved: P8.

- FP7 Sis Catalyst: Aims to foster and support ethical, effective and sustainable engagement between children and the social, cultural, political, scientific and educational institutions that make the decisions that shape their futures. CCHub will use the methodologies to strengthen children's role in society.
- SPARKS RRI Tools: Sparks is an awareness-raising project to show Europeans that they can get involved in science. CCHub partner involved: P2.
- H2020 HYPATIA: Will create a toolkit of gender-inclusive activities, and guidelines in gender-sensitivity for teachers and educators of young people. These tools will inform the creation of the gender-equity training for the CCHub network. CCHub partner involved: P2.
- H2020 Hack the Brain: Aims to build and facilitate a growing community of 'makers' that appropriate new technology and put it to societal use. CCHub will build on these best practices to organise hackathons with community stakeholders. CCHub partner involved: P2.
- WISE Learners Voice Programme: Equips youth to take on leading roles in their fields and in the world of education and focuses on building skills education, social entrepreneurship, leadership, and communication. CCHub partner involved: P1.

1.3.3 Gender considerations

The Treaty of the European Union aims to eliminate gender inequality and promote equal opportunities for women. In accordance with the Treaty of Amsterdam (1997) and other EU policy reports (EUR 2002/2), as well as the UN Global Goals, establishing equality between men and women is a priority. The CCHub project is committed to incorporating the principles of gender mainstreaming throughout the entire project, giving equal consideration to the different life patterns, needs and interests of male and female participants and project members. To this end, the CCHub project will take into account:

- **The different needs and responsibilities of men and women regarding care.** This includes differences in mobility and balance in paid work and care tasks.
- **Unpaid work carried out by women,** in particular reproductive work carried out in the home. For CCHub it is important to emphasize and explicitly recognise the gender gap in terms of unpaid tasks.
- **The gendered nature of technological innovation:** A strong link exists between the attributes of technology (and innovation) and masculine culture. Economic development often prioritises masculine innovation that values growth-oriented profits, while more feminized knowledge and practice targeting equality or community well-being are undervalued. CCHub will emphasize and recognize those forms of (social) innovation that are not high-tech but equally important.
- **Difference in access to technology and technology-related skills.** Important differences still exist in skills and motivation of women in relation to technology use. Where necessary, CCHub will offer special training for different users.

CCHub will incorporate a **gender lens** in its methodology, and consider how groups, procedures and the focus on innovation may limit women's participation. CCHub will monitor the representation of genders within the project team and will support consortium members and collaborators with caring responsibilities by ensuring meetings at family-friendly hours, and facilitating family-friendly working arrangements within all partner organisations.

All CCHub events and activities will be inclusive and equitable for all genders and orientations and are developed and executed according to gender equity recommendations (using Toolkits from H2020 Hypatia and IASC Gender Handbook). Gender equity guidelines will be provided to all CCHub managers as well as all CCHub programme participants. Gender balance will also be considered in CCHub activities relating to participation in activities.

1.4 Ambition

According to the EU Education & Training 2020 (ET2020) framework^{xxi}, Europe has four key objectives in the areas of education and training, all four of which CCHubs aims to address: (1) Making lifelong learning and mobility a reality; (2) Improving the quality and efficiency of education and training; (3) Promoting equity, social cohesion, and active citizenship; (4) Enhancing creativity and innovation, including entrepreneurship, at all levels of education and training.

Co Creation Hub provides a stepping stone for European society towards the realisation of equity, social cohesion, and active citizenship by enhancing creativity and innovation, including social entrepreneurship in Europe. The project will improve the standards of education and training in social entrepreneurship. The 4 main ambitions of CCHub are:

A1. Young people have the necessary skills to become a valuable part of the European workforce, and the vision to become innovators and entrepreneurs

CCHub believes that it is possible to empower young people to meet the needs for skills required for the (near-)future workforce. CCHub will introduce new skills – like creativity, risk taking adaptability and innovation capacity, problem solving skills, effective teamwork and sharing information and knowledge – in a innovative way to thousands of young people. Moreover, the training resources produced by the project will enable a much bigger fraction to become innovators and entrepreneurs.

A2. Youth contribute to the wellbeing of their communities

At the end of CCHub at least 8000 young people from disadvantaged communities will be equipped with skills to tackle European and local challenges. They will be empowered to take risks in addressing local challenges in a collaborative and creative way. The CCHub approach can then be widely used by educators, community leaders and youth themselves to tackle similar local issues.

A3. A more integrated and inclusive society for all young people

CCHub allows youth to be more embedded in their local community workforce. The project provides a unique hub connecting youth groups, schools, families, local authorities and SMEs. The project's focus on training less privileged youth to solve community challenges simultaneously empowers youth to be part of society and allows youth to address local issues, leading to a more integrated and inclusive society.

A4. Social Entrepreneurship & Innovation are part of formal, non-formal and informal education, from early childhood to Lifelong Learning

CCHub is implemented by some of the leaders in Europe's social entrepreneurship and science education networks. By bringing these communities together CCHub aims to develop an innovative educational and training skills programme. By the end of the project CCHub aims to have validated its approach to innovation and entrepreneurship skills training through co-creation of social projects. This approach can then be used by other education communities and integrated in relevant curriculums, from primary and secondary schools to Lifelong Learning. The CCHub consortium will work closely with policy-makers to ensure that in the near future Social Entrepreneurship & Innovation are part of education curriculums across Europe.

2. Impact

2.1 Expected impacts

CCHub will create new collaborations to engage disadvantaged youth across Europe that will foster social entrepreneurship and innovation education and skills development. The expected impacts of the CCHub project are divided into short, medium and long-term effects in the following sections. The actions of the project will contribute to *a more skilled society and for young people to have a better awareness of and interest in social innovation and entrepreneurship*. Each section also estimates the impact of CCHub actions for each target group. All CCHub actions are time-based, measurable and trackable, realistic and achievable during the duration of the project and will be assessed in terms of quantity and quality.

2.1.1 Contribution towards impacts mentioned in the call topic

The following table summarizes the project’s contribution and impact.

Expected Impact Identified by the call	CCHub Contributions
<p><i>(1) Pave the way for innovating learning and teaching practices, so that innovation skills are part of a person's education, formal and informal, at schools and interacting communities as well as on-line.</i></p>	<p><i>Interacting communities:</i> Each partner will work with disadvantaged youth communities during the pilot phase. The dissemination of the model and resources through the CCHub website will allow additional community implementation.</p> <p><i>Schools action:</i> School pilots will be co-developed and implemented in at least 12 schools by P5: Ashoka (IE). The schools model will be also exploited to other European countries and beyond, through P5-ASH’s existing “Changemaker Schools” network consisting of over 200 schools globally (for countries without a Changemaker School we will initiate e-twinning between schools).</p> <p><i>Online:</i> The CCHub online platform will have a number of distinct elements: video case-studies from initial participating schools & communities showcasing their social enterprises and innovations; a MOOC hosted on Coursera which allows schools or community groups to follow the model of engagement through the co-creation & skills training steps to develop their own social enterprise; professional development tools and pedagogical guides for teachers and trainers/community leaders; a link to a conversational forum for participants and potential new users (Facebook group or other interactive platform determined by the youth participants).</p>
<p><i>(2) Boost innovation and entrepreneurship capacity, bringing together many stakeholders from education, traditional business, the social and service economy and volunteering schemes.</i></p>	<p>Boost innovation & entrepreneurship capacity by fostering innovation environments in the communities involved. Stakeholders from schools, community groups and programmes, local enterprises, research organisations and voluntary civil society organisations will be facilitated by the project partners during the pilot phase. The engagement will on social innovation by the young people involved, who will shape and constrain ideas, and build innovation capacity.</p>

<p><i>(3) Empower young innovators across Europe, provide them with innovative business models and tools to engage in society and channel their energies to create future opportunities.</i></p>	<p><i>Empowerment:</i> The project will empower 8000 young people develop innovation & entrepreneurial skills through hands-on practice, online training and other training resources. <i>Provide for innovative business models:</i> Social innovations developed in the pilot phase will address problems specific to the co-creators and thus will be unique and innovative. Each youth project group will be mentored to co-develop their own business model. Each CCHub partner will create targeted business models to ensure sustainability of the local/regional CCHub activities beyond project closure.</p> <p><i>Give [young people] tools to engage in society and channel their energies to create opportunities for the future:</i> By using the CCHub resources, tools and guidelines to create a social innovation project, young people will engage with their local community in a meaningful way. The interdisciplinary nature of the projects and the inclusion of maker and tinkering activities, as well as the arts, will open up pathways to new possible areas of interest for them to channel their energies.</p>
<p><i>(4) In the long run the topic contributes to higher youth employment and to creating new markets and new jobs.</i></p>	<p>By using the CCHub approach to create a social enterprise, young people will be active participants in the entrepreneurial process, will be equipped to tackle European as well as local challenges, and will gain valuable skills to increase their opportunities in the job market. By participating in the co-creation process, local enterprises and young people will work together collaboratively, with youth embedded in their local community workforce. This will result in increased youth employment in the area. There is potential for some of the social enterprises developed by the participants to spin out into successful start-ups, and for the skills gained by youth to be applied to the development of future ventures and enterprises, thus creating new markets and new jobs.</p>
<p><i>(5) The knowledge generated as a result of the actions should be disseminated across Europe to benefit the largest numbers of young innovators.</i></p>	<p>As well as the social enterprises developed by the participants in the initial pilot, the online open-source CCHub platform will serve young innovators in schools and communities across Europe with an array of social innovation activities, ideas and pedagogical tools as well as a platform for discussion and sharing. This CCHub Platform will include co-creation guides, localization guides, educational activities, and professional development guides for educators to support the creation and implementation of social innovation across Europe. There will also be a link to the academic research that will inform policy and practice for entrepreneurship education for responsible citizenship. CCHub resources will be disseminated through existing repositories, as well as through partner networks.</p>

2.1.2 Impacts by Category

II. Impacts on the beneficiaries

Girls and boys from disadvantaged groups

CCHub will promote partnerships between the community groups, families, local enterprises and research institutes with the goal of engaging them in the social innovation processes, thus promoting education and skills training as part of local community development.

- Short Term: Young people who are part of the initial pilot phase will gain direct training and develop innovation and entrepreneurship skills. By participating in a making entrepreneurial program, students get to “touch and feel” the results. Their ideas can grow quickly into real innovative products and solutions with the potential to develop into real enterprises or start-ups. Participation in the pilot phase will also serve to increase independence, creativity, and self-esteem. The young people will work closely with researchers and local businesses and industries who will be engaged through the facilitation by the local consortium partner. These local stakeholders will help young people to contribute to community well-being by giving the students opportunities to learn about their work, to receive support and guidance from them. They can also help the students promote and disseminate their social innovation projects through their channels and resources (e.g., a display in a local business location or article in a university newsletter). This will contribute to young people's understanding of innovation, entrepreneurship, STEAM and their applicability to real life issues. Moreover, CCHubs will ensure that boys and girls are equally involved in CCHub activities.
- Long Term: Young people who later access the online resources can use them to develop their own social innovation capabilities. Some of the community groups who take part in the pilot phase will continue to offer the training to further groups of young people. By participating in CCHub it is expected that students will be aware of potential scientific and entrepreneurial careers and be equipped with tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices regarding science and technology beyond the duration of the project. WP4: EVALUATE will produce the necessary data for future studies to assess to what extent these impact estimators are met.

Schools - Students, Teachers, Parents

CCHub will promote partnerships between the education community, families, local enterprises, research institutes and the local community in order to engage them in the teaching and learning processes around social innovation in schools and to promote education as part of local community development. Through P5-ASH, CCHub activities will be implemented in “Changemaker Schools”. Implementing maker-based activities focussing on social innovation will greatly enhance and complement the curricula of Changemaker Schools and address identified needs.

A. Short Term:

Students in primary and secondary education (6-18 years old): Studies such as the longitudinal HighScope-Perry study^{xxii} show that high-quality early childhood education can lead to economic and social gains, as well as lower crime rates in participants from low-income families. Through the CCHub, students are engaged in meaningful STEAM and tinkering experiences that have an influence on their direct communities. The co-creation element will show students that they have a say in what they learn about. As with the young people engaged through the community groups, schools will work closely with researchers and local businesses and industries. The overall CCHub experience and the exploration of the complex interchange between science, art, technology and design through hands on activities with a social innovation focus will encourage a deep

understanding of the skills of critical thinking, problem solving, collaboration and creativity - all skills that are essential in today's world.

Teachers: During the pilot phase, teachers in Changemaker Schools where the values of empathy, creativity, teamwork and leadership are already valued, will work to guide students to use these skills and to employ maker-centred STEAM learning to develop social innovation projects. The upskilling of teachers in areas such as coding, design, engineering and STEAM will also allow teachers to develop and increase their skills in inquiry-based science education, problem-based learning, and student-centred inquiry. Teachers are closely involved in the co-creation of CCHub resources and activities and will receive training on gender equity. As highlighted by the Entrepreneurship Education at School in Europe report, there is also a general lack of guidelines for entrepreneurial education across Europe^{xxiii} and the provision of these through the CCHub platform will enable teachers to better incorporate entrepreneurship education in their practice.

Parents: Through the school pilot, the parents of the participating students will also be engaged as the young people decide on issues of importance to explore and on problems to be solved through STEAM. This will lead to a more scientifically engaged society and a more innovative environment as communities embrace the idea that everyone can be a changemaker.

B. Long Term:

School governance: Due to the recognition of Changemaker Schools and the societal value placed on a school being socially conscious and aware, more schools will adopt the changemaker attitudes and values, as well as using the CCHub resources and guidelines to develop activities and to encourage co-creation, maker learning and transdisciplinary approaches to problem-solving.

Teacher Continuous Professional Development: CCHub partners and teachers will provide training in the use of CCHub resources and pedagogical models at national teacher events, for teachers beyond direct regional reach.

Students: Around 50% of the students participating in CCHub activities will be selecting their post-secondary school studies and careers within 5 years of the closure of the project. CCHub activities will increase participants' awareness of entrepreneurship opportunities and scientific careers. It is expected that CCHub activities will have an *impact on students' career decisions*, contributing towards the ERA objectives of increasing the numbers of scientists and researchers in Europe, as well as contributing to ET2020 objectives for education and training^{xxiv}.

Impact on wider society of CCHub approach in schools: Changemaker schools have been identified as schools that are creating systemic change from the ground up. They have identified that the empowerment of pupils and teachers to work together in innovative ways for the common good, is how society will change for the better. Changemaker schools have recognised that the social and economic challenges in the world are complex and there is an urgent need to rethink education. Changemaker schools understand that children need to be educated and equipped to be part of the solution. Implementing maker-activities with a focus on social innovation would be an important programme in which to enhance these ambitions. The issue of poverty is a complex one, and four of the Changemaker schools are designated as serving children at high risk of poverty. These schools have identified a significant need to look at creative ways to address poverty and education in the area of consumption, and the creative re-use of materials, which will be address through the CCHub approach, and can be replicated in other similar schools across Europe.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project (M36), 55 teachers involved in co-creation of CCHub resources, 1100 teachers aware of CCHub activities, 550 teachers trained and 20 open access resources available for teacher use. Over the duration of the project, at least 75% of CCHub activities are co-organised and co-run

by teachers. Each CCHub manager will collect data about the participation of teachers in CCHub activities and other relevant information according to the guidelines provided by the Work Package 6.

Community organisations:

- **Short Term:** The leaders from the cooperating community organisations^{xxv} participating in the initial pilot phase will have direct contact with the consortium partners, will gain skills through participation in the kick-off training, will help to co-create the framework for engagement with the communities (D4.3?), and will participate in the co-creation of the social innovation projects with the young people during the pilot phase. This means the community leaders will be skilled and motivated to continue to offer the CCHub approach to new groups of young people, and will be able to work with youth who have completed the programme to become trainers or mentors, thus ensuring the sustainability of the project within their organisation. Through the establishment of links with local enterprises they may be able to secure sponsorship or support for voluntary activities. Successful implementation of the CCHub project and effective dissemination of the results could lead to increased membership or subscription, and increased government, EU or philanthropic funding.
- **Long Term:** It has been proven that young people learn well from role-models and examples that they identify with. Through the case studies of social innovation and enterprises developed during the pilot phase, communities across Europe will be inspired to implement the CCHub methodology within their own locality.

Local small and medium enterprises (SMEs)

- **Short Term:** SMEs could benefit by promoting social innovation projects which align with their offerings. An example would be a project promoting healthy eating; a local supermarket could promote the initiative by placing recipe cards created by the project in their fruit and vegetable section, which would also benefit them by increasing their sales. By participating in the pilot phase of CCHub, SMEs would have the opportunity to improve their standing within the community and to affect social change in their locality. By participating in co-creation workshop, they gain an opportunity to become more aware of issues pertaining to their customer base, which may lead to a necessary change in marketing or sale strategies. SMEs could also use the project to develop their Corporate Social Responsibility mandate. CCHub will implement several STEAM making and tinkering activities which will demonstrate the convenience of the circular economy and the positive effects of creating an enabling and protected ecosystem where private sector, public sector and third sector cooperate and share a converging vision. CCHub will connect young people with local businesses and meaningful responsible actors from the private sector. Students will gain experience in real-life, responsible local business projects while local businesses have a vested interest to connect with the future workforce and promote their activities.
- **Long Term:** Increased innovation capacity in the locality leads to a skilled and employable workforce with whom they have already nurtured a working relationship. Awareness of CCHub as a useful mode of engagement within local networks of industry such as regional Chambers of Commerce, which represent both SMEs and larger companies.

Impact estimators: 110 activities connecting schools with local businesses. The number of uses of the technical equipment by local businesses will also be collected and monitored. Each CCHub manager will collect data about the participation of local industry and other enterprises in CCHub activities and other relevant information according to the guidelines provided by the WP6. Whenever possible data will be collected by the CCHub managers on the added value that CCHub will bring to the local businesses, this will be done in close collaboration with P3-IH.

NGOs and voluntary or Civil Society Organisations

Increased funding opportunities, new/stronger community ties, and links with schools in a particular area are anticipated outcomes.

Universities/research institutions

Universities and research institutions benefit by developing new connections with organisations willing to participate in Community-Based Participatory Research, Science Shops, Citizen Science projects and other Responsible Research and Innovation initiatives. The CCHub's contribution to a more socially responsible and scientifically literate society will improve the public perception of research and innovation, increase the public engagement with important research being carried out in their area, and instill a sense of empowerment for the community to play an active role in this research.

Impact estimators: 5 researchers involved in delivery of 110 activities with youth and community participants.

I2 Impact beyond beneficiaries

CCHub will implement actions which will have an impact on students and wider society over a longer timescale than the project itself, as described in the call. In the medium term, CCHub activities support citizens and future researchers in using tools and developing skills that will help them make informed decisions. Data will be collected in WP2: EVALUATE to provide a baseline measurement for such long-term studies and "longitudinal assessments".

Wider Society

Actions: The wider society will have the opportunity to be involved in the CCHub initially (M9-M17) by participating in the development of the social innovation projects, through the co-creation workshops organised in each location. The local users will also be invited to participate in community hackathons as the projects are developed, and to become end-users of the social innovation which has relevance to their own community. These activities will focus on social interactions and dialogue, and scientific and cultural exchange. Members of society will complement skills and competences through participation in community-based learning experiences. Media and social media will directly target young people, with the scope of promoting awareness of the CCHub concept and methodology. By participating in CCHub it is expected that citizens will be equipped beyond the duration of the project with tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices regarding innovation, science and technology. They will be exposed to a co-creation and dialogue format that can be used in other contexts beyond those of science, education and entrepreneurship.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project (M36), 5500 members of the wider society (not including initial Local Action phase participants) have become aware of CCHub actions and the resulting social innovations, an average of 500 per CCHub. WP2: EVALUATE will produce the necessary data for future studies to assess the extent to which this impact is met.

CCHub Partners and Network: Coordinators, project managers and facilitators.

During the kick-off and throughout the project, CCHub will make expert training available to coordinators, project managers and facilitators on relevant topics, through the expertise within the consortium which will be shared across the network, as well through established connections with other relevant EU projects such as Erasmus+ Tinkering EU and the Hypatia project. The CCHub consortium will be a community of practice for STEAM education in the context of social innovation. CCHub network members will also become part of the FP7 RRI Tools community of practice. The ongoing relationships with the cooperating organisations will lead to strengthened community ties for the partner organisations.

Impact Estimator: CCHub project will employ and train at least 13 project managers or facilitators.

Media

Whenever possible local and national media will be invited to the local CCHub activities. A number of press releases will be issued by all the partners (in coordination with WP6:DISSEMINATE. Social innovation projects will also be exposed to media coverage as they will be showcased through existing large events such as Ars Electronica Festival, and EU Researchers' Night, as well as local events (eg: P2 (TCD-IE) and cooperating organisation Axis Ballymun will leverage existing connection with Ballymun Youth Community Arts Festival to showcase results).

Impact Estimator: 55 media outlets (both traditional and online) will be engaged, including social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and Snapchat and recorded/tracked by online statistics (i.e. Google Analytics).

I3 Impact on European innovation and entrepreneurship skills training and curriculum

According to the EACEA report *Entrepreneurship Education at School in Europe* (2012) "...a common European understanding and approach to learning outcomes for entrepreneurship education is still to be developed". CCHub will address this need by developing easily-adaptable pedagogical models focusing on key learning outcomes, and by increasing the availability of resources for innovation and entrepreneurship skills education for teachers. By leveraging existing connections with curriculum authorities at regional and national level, and by lobbying governmental Education departments in partner countries, CCHub pedagogical guidelines and modules could be implemented as part of the national aims and strategies as outlined for each country in *Entrepreneurship Education at School in Europe* (2012)^{xxvi}. A push to embed CCHub activities into the core curricula of primary and secondary schools across Europe, will ensure that it is treated as an integral part of the long-term educational system rather than as a standalone, and potentially short-term, initiative.

Furthermore, the method of engaging with groups of disadvantaged youth in informal or non-formal learning settings through non-traditional educational models means that CCHub will be very attractive to education beyond the scope of mainstream schools. As part of the dissemination activities, CCHub partners engage with organisations and education and training bodies across Europe to promote the incorporation of CCHub modules, resources and methodologies in vocational skills training, back-to-education programmes, community education, prison education, adult learning centres, and special educational needs learning.

All the guides, activity plans and other relevant resources will be available on the CCHub websites and national, European and international open educational resource repositories, namely Scientix, OERCommons, Open Education Europa, TES Education and InformalScience.org^{xxvii}. These resources will be promoted through national and European networks of informal and non-formal education providers such as Scientix, Ecsite, TEMI, EU Space Awareness, EUSEA^{xxviii}, etc.

Impact estimators: At the end of the project, 500 educators have used CCHub resources. CCHub will collect information about number of downloads of these resources and interactions with the informal and non-formal education communities.

I4 Impacts on European society and current societal challenges

CCHub not only helps to create a society which is more skilled, but it does this through social action and societal awareness. All communities involved with the local action pilot phase will have increased awareness of, and engagement with societal challenges at a local, European and global level. The interaction with local research institutes will contribute to a more scientifically and socially aware and engaged society. The opportunity to participate directly in the process of finding solutions to societal challenges through co-creation will empower society at all levels. The use of the social innovation projects could lead to improvement in the quality of life of the users, which leads to a healthier society. Increased skills and

employment levels due to the project will lead to overall improvement of the innovation capacity of a community, a healthy entrepreneurial ecosystem, and a reduction in poverty.

Impact pillars: Economic & Commercial:

1. Approx. 30 new social enterprises (start-ups) during the Local Action phase in 9 countries.
2. Potential for the social enterprises to develop into viable and profitable startups.
3. Through efficient dissemination measures in local communities, and leveraging of consortium partners' networks, there is potential for businesses/industries to invest in the social enterprises or to collaborate with the creators to improve or scale up.
4. 12 jobs (FTEs) will be funded through employment of project facilitators and managers in 11 consortium partners.
5. Employment opportunities will be created by increasing the skills of the young people engaged in the pilot phase, and exposing them to the entrepreneurial process - making them employable in the social, service or manufacturing economy.

Impact pillars: Societal

1. Social innovation will be embedded in communities, and will highlight paths to immediate and practical solutions to local issues, thus empowering the community to be agents for change and promoting an innovation environment.
2. Maker activities and maker-based learning for younger children and in schools will increase engagement with STEM, particularly non-formal STEM learning, and the possibilities of transdisciplinary activities e.g. STEM+Arts.
3. Public awareness and understanding of STEM and social sciences and humanities increased through engagement between communities and research institutes
4. Increased capacities and skills for participating community groups, NGOs, civil society organisations, support groups and voluntary organisations.
5. Quality of life improved for the end users of the social innovations, as the specific problems addressed by the projects are discussed, addressed and potentially solved.
6. CCHub specifically increases community development, and supports culture through the trans-disciplinary nature of training - e.g. STEAM

Impact pillars: International Engagement

1. Social innovation by participants will specifically address societal challenges and sustainable development goals at a local level)
2. Problems will be tackled by similar communities in different parts of Europe, and the evaluation through this wide-lens will contribute to widely adaptable resources and guidelines which can be used throughout the Innovation Union.

Impact pillars: Policy & Public Service

1. Policy decisions, changes to legislation/regulations/guidelines informed by research evidence
2. Change to education policy or school curricula to incorporate CCHub pedagogical models and resources as part of a broader push to improve innovation and entrepreneurship education across Europe.

Overall Impact Estimates: At the end of the project (M36) 200 000 students have participated in CCHub activities, in average 18 000 students per CCHub. At least 90% of all students participating in CCHub activities will be aware of STEAM related careers. Each CCHub manager will collect data about the participation of students in CCHub activities according to the guidelines provided by Work Package P2: EVALUTE.

2.1.3 External factors that might influence feasibility of expected impacts

CCHub is aware of external factors that might pose challenges in achieving the expected impacts. CCHub has put necessary measures in place to overcome these risks:

Low activity of the target audience in the community-based participatory workshops: Activities provided by the CCHub project and online platform will bring active encouragement, co-creation and targeted campaigning of these activities by the partners and their member institutions, and will largely involve existing partners and collaborators, thus mitigating this concern to a great extent.

Language barriers: this is a problem for sharing across Europe, but also for working with migrant populations in cities, which will be dealt with by ensuring translation and localisation in the necessary situations. CCHub resources will be initially provided in 10 languages, and additional translations will be encouraged.

Slow uptake: It often takes a long time to get stakeholders to agree to be involved, and even longer to get them to act. This could pose a problem for the timing and operative outcomes of the project. The project will leverage existing networks, partners and collaborators of the consortium, as well as initiating new partnerships, thus mitigating this concern to a great extent.

2.2 Measures to maximise impact

2.2.1 Dissemination and exploitation of results

The main aim of CCHub dissemination is to create value for all identified target groups, with a focus on youth (including schools, enterprises, civil and wider society, local communities, science communicators, museum educators, etc.) and beyond. Ultimately, dissemination^{xxix} will ensure that the CCHub project results are exploited to **improve learning and teaching of social entrepreneurship** and **build community partnerships** that contribute to the **development of youth's skills** and empower youth to tackle local community challenges, to **increase youth's employability and competitiveness**.

To achieve this goal, CCHub dissemination will share social entrepreneurship & innovation training best practices and disseminate the open source CCHub Toolkits, including all resources, guides and MOOC. The development and implementation of the detailed exploitation and communication plan (WP6) will ensure widespread dissemination. CCHub materials will be available in at least 10 languages and will be disseminated through a variety of existing channels, networks, and repositories targeting (formal, informal and non-formal) education, enterprise, research and governments (at local, regional, national and European level). Cooperation between the partners during and after the project timeline is key in the dissemination plan: each CCHub partner will collaborate to disseminate CCHub assets through their own channels and networks, locally, nationally, European and international level. In addition, each local CCHub partner will develop a suitable sustainability plan (WP6) in collaboration with regional Impact Hubs and local government (through existing and new partnerships), to maximize the legacy of CCHub results.

Dissemination and exploitation activities are performed by all CCHub consortium partners. In particular, WP4, WP5 and WP6 have specific tasks and deliverables related to fostering the community involved in CCHub, sharing CCHub resources, results and ensuring the continuation, exploitation and legacy of the project beyond closure. Specific communication channels and measures to reach these community stakeholders are described in section 2.2.2.

CCHub Outcomes for exploitation

The following (open source) CCHub products and activities are identified as main assets for exploitation during and after the project timeline:

- The **CCHub Toolkits**: guides for full development and implementation of the CCHub programme generalised for any community or school, including best practices, case study videos (highlighting collaborations with local enterprises), and all CCHub educational resources and facilitation guides on co-creation, innovation, (social) entrepreneurship, business plan development tools, gender equity recommendations, maker activities, and teacher professional development.
- **CCHub MOOC**: open access Massive Open Online Course on social entrepreneurship & innovation for youth (created by P1-UL in collaboration with Coursera) to support implementation of CCHub Toolkits by educators, teachers, youth group leaders, community leaders and youth themselves.
- All local **CCHub Events**, workshops and activities
- All CCHub youth **CCHub social enterprises** developed during the project, and the related solutions/outcomes for local communities
- CCHub **sustainability plans**
- CCHub **evaluation and academic research results** in open access journals, to inform policy and school governance
- The **CCHub Digital Platform**, through which all CCHub assets and communication will be shared, as well as through extensive partner networks.

After project

The main results of CCHub will be exploited during Phase III, through a variety of actions, including the business plans developed as a part of the CCHub project. The main aim is to keep the 11 CCHub partners providing training beyond the 3 initial project years and for organisations, schools, and individual or groups of young people across Europe to exploit the resources, outcomes and experience from the EU-funded project. The CCHub Digital Platform will be maintained for a minimum of 3 years after end of project, supported by the use of existing web frameworks by CCHub coordinator (P1 - UL). The implementation of sustainability plans of local CCHub projects, in collaboration with local government and local Impact Hubs, will support the continuation of CCHub training programmes in local youth communities, and the continued dissemination of CCHub activities. In addition, CCHub partners will study new opportunities for funding based on the results of the project. Finally, CCHub partners will support the continuous dissemination of the project through the usual channels of information (including partner websites, publications, mailing lists, social media, etc.), as described in further detail in section 2.2.2.

Co-creation of context-adapted local programmes by each CCHub partner will be led by local educational community, with the involvement of local government and industry at all stages of the creative process. This leads to local ownership over the project. In combination with the creation of a sustainable business plan for each CCHub partner, this will support the legacy of the project, and the continuation of CCHub programmes beyond the lifetime of the project. The open source accessibility of all supporting material created during the project will allow for the reproducibility of an CCHub in other regions. Moreover, WP6 will study potential exploitation of the intellectual property generated during the project to support the legacy and sustainability of the local CCHub programmes.

2.2.2 Communication activities

Communication of CCHub activities, events, products and resources will be an integral part of the project, covered by WP6. To maximise impact, CCHub will exploit an extremely broad range of top-down and bottom-up approaches in several networks (education, social innovation and entrepreneurship) for dissemination of the project (see Table 2.2). The fact that the consortium partner organisations have leading roles in all of these broader networks will enhance the impact of the dissemination (e.g.: P1-UL leads science education networks, P2-TCD leads science & art networks, P3-IH-IT leads entrepreneurship & innovation networks, P5-ASH leads social entrepreneurship networks). Where possible, dissemination will occur using digital platforms and tools. In addition to the significant local impact of CCHub community

programmes, the CCHub project shall exploit its broad range of networks to attain as wide as possible a reach with its resources within partner countries, Europe and globally.

The CCHub communication activities are structured around four elements: vision, strategy, execution and impact assessment. The communications strategy will be developed in detail during the first six months of the project. Implementation of this strategy will be ensured by P1-UL through the internal online community (such as Basecamp or Yammer), and regular monthly online contact with the CCHub project partners. The strategy will include: (1) A comprehensive mapping of all partners channels, including social media; (2) The definition of common messages and editorial principles; (3) The definition of common materials (printed and digital); (4) A timeline reviewed every six months based on the key indicators mentioned; (5) A checklist of communications activities to be undertaken by each partner

The **CCHub web platform** will be based on an innovative open source web framework for the management, distribution and dissemination of information, news and educational resources and activities as well managing events, stocks and other relevant information for CCHubs. This web framework will be based on open-source software *django* and has been co-developed by Leiden University (P1-UL). These frameworks have been used for some of the most visited educational and outreach websites in Europe, such as the ESA/NASA Hubble Space Telescope, ESO, Universe Awareness, EU Space Awareness and others across the world. The web framework will allow the project to develop a cohesive web presence and prepare websites in (at least) 10 CCHub languages, to support local dissemination initiatives. The format of the existing web frameworks makes expansion to other languages simple, fast and low-cost development. Specific modules to produce, manage, translate and distribute educational materials have been developed for the existing web framework. The framework allows the author of the resource to update the content of the resource and automatically produce the necessary output files in the necessary formats (example: html, print ready PDFs, ePUBs (for eReaders like iPads, Kindles or iPhones) and also source files and *doc* files for easy translation). This will also allow a direct update of the activities through an API (application programming interface) to the generic resources databases (such as OERCommons, Scientix, TES, ISSU, Slideshare). The web platform will also support local CCHub partners on their path toward financial sustainability, through the inclusion of digital business and entrepreneurship tools for the development of a Business Model Canvas, Value Proposition Canvas and Logical Framework.

All CCHub resources, publications, research, data and products will follow closely the guidelines on open access to scientific publications and research data in Horizon 2020 provided by the European Commission. Products and resources will be open source and where relevant produced using a Creative Commons License (Attribution-Share Alike 4.0), following recommendations from the European Commission on Open Education^{xxx} and Open Access^{xxxi}. Where possible, we shall also make the source files publicly available in common open repositories. This licensing will encourage adaptation and localisation of all CCHub products, and will allow for derivatives of the project to be used for commercial purposes and to support youth and local communities. All educational resources will be open educational resources (OER) and scientific publications will be submitted to Open Access journals.

The sections below describe all **CCHub target audiences, dissemination channels and the measures** that will be applied to reach them. The sections also describe a set of communication products that will be created to achieve the expected impact for each specific target group.

Target audiences and dissemination channels

Students: To reach relevant youth groups, relevant local CCHub have partnered with local schools and local groups. Students will be reached through the partnerships with schools, through parent associations and through existing networks for young people, such as Scouts groups, after school programmes, and other

locally relevant youth organisations. To reach students, CCHub will distribute posters and brochures (locally), develop an active presence on social media, and disseminate specifically to parents, teachers and schools (see sections below on formal educators and school governance), as well as explore possibilities for guerrilla marketing to reach youth. CCHub will also explore the possibility to include CCHub activities for youth in Youthpass activities of Erasmus+ Youth in Action. For this target group, main relevant CCHub assets are: The CCHub Toolkits, CCHub MOOC, CCHub Events, CCHub social enterprise projects, and CCHub Digital Platform.

Formal educators: To effectively reach formal educators throughout Europe, CCHub will apply a local, national, European and international approach. Locally, CCHub partners will use the local partnerships and leverage their existing communication channels (e.g. teachers-centred websites and publications, textbook publishers) and teacher networks (e.g. national teachers associations). Local partners will also disseminate CCHub activities, products and resources at regional and national levels, through networks and at relevant events (E.g.: teachers congresses or meetings). CCHub partners will also approach local vocational school and provide information and teacher training at national teacher events. Relevant information and resources will also be disseminated through existing teacher networks and existing repositories on European and international level, by WP6. Each CCHub partner will also exploit their existing teacher networks to expand CCHub reach of formal educators (see Table 2.2). Finally, CCHub will leverage its membership on relevant formal education social media groups (e.g. Science teachers in Europe and Galileo Teachers Facebook groups) to share CCHub resources.

For this target group, main relevant assets are: The CCHub Toolkits (including best practices, training and guides), CCHub MOOC, CCHub Events, CCHub sustainability plans, evaluation and academic research, and CCHub Digital Platform. CCHub will disseminate newsletters, short articles, posters and leaflets, as well as develop an active social media presence to reach formal educators (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and explore new media if relevant at that time). All CCHub products and resources will be freely available on the Digital CCHub platform to download, adapt and share.

School-level governance: CCHub will partner with local school management boards. Through these partnerships, CCHub will engage school-level governance in Collaborative Social Entrepreneurship & Innovation activities with other societal actors, and increasing their awareness of the importance of Social Entrepreneurship and related skills to empower students for the future. CCHub will also use its networks with local government and the existing collaborations of local partners to involve school governance in CCHub activities at all levels, from development to activity implementation. Local CCHub partners will primarily foster in person contacts with the representatives of school governance. For this target group, main assets are: the CCHub approach, the CCHub Toolkits, CCHub MOOC, CCHub Events, CCHub social enterprise projects, CCHub sustainability plans, CCHub Digital Platform and evaluation and academic research, to inform policy.

University educators and researchers: CCHub partners are part of several university and research networks (see Table 2.2) and in addition, all local CCHub partners have established partnerships with research institutes. Through these partnerships, CCHub will involve university educators and researchers in the co-development and implementation of CCHub activities throughout the CCHub network in 10 countries, and facilitate collaborations between researchers and local enterprise. Specifically, CCHub will exploit existing mailing lists (e.g. Leiden University internal mailing list and alumni mailing list), websites of partner research networks research unions (e.g. European Physical Society, International Astronomical Union), and academies of science and humanities (e.g. ALLEA^{xxxiii}) and leverage participation at relevant conferences, to reach this target audience. CCHub partners (1-UL, 2-TCD) also run training for scientists involved in science communication activities (for example JCOM Masterclasses^{xxxiii}, Thesis in Three^{xxxiv} and masters

programmes in Science Communication^{xxxv}), and will disseminate CCHub project results in such occasions in the years to come.

CCHub will send email newsletters, publish updates on existing websites and disseminate posters and leaflets at relevant events. For this target group, main relevant CCHub assets are: the CCHub approach, the CCHub Toolkits, the Digital Platform, CCHub events and activities, and CCHub evaluation and academic research.

Local industry and commerce: CCHubs will partner with local enterprises or chambers of commerce to support sustainable development of local industry. Whenever possible, CCHub will work closely with Maker professionals (e.g. carpenters, electricians, farmers, engineers, artists). For this target group, main CCHub assets are: the CCHub approach, the CCHub Digital Platform, CCHub events and activities, CCHub youth social enterprises, CCHub sustainability plans.

Local and/or regional government and other policy makers: Reaching policy makers, local and national advocacy lobbying. CCHub academic research and evaluation results to inform policy. For this target group, main CCHub assets are: the CCHub approach, the CCHub Toolkits, the CCHub Digital Platform, CCHub youth social enterprises, CCHub sustainability plans, CCHub evaluation/research results, to inform policy and school governance.

Civil society: CCHub has partnered with 35 civil society associations (see table 4.1b), who will be closely involved in co-developing activities. Whenever, possible, CCHub will collaborate with local makerspaces and repair cafes to leverage on their experience. Art and creative professionals, Clubs and community groups based around interests like computers, model trains, and knitting. For this target group, main assets are: the CCHub approach, the CCHub Digital Platform, CCHub events and activities and CCHub youth social enterprises.

Wider society: Local CCHub projects will create an accessible and encouraging learning environment for local youth and their communities. In general, youth social enterprises developed within the CCHub programme will benefit wider society by addressing local community challenges. To reach families, CCHub will provide an inviting environment for family members (e.g. by offering a separate play area for children who may be too young to participate and finding times that work for families). For this target group, main assets are: the CCHub Digital Platform, CCHub events and activities, CCHub youth enterprises.

Informal and non-formal education communities (national, European and global): The Digital CCHub platform will serve as a common repository for all CCHub products and resources. To maximise reach, CCHub will also publish all open access resources on existing repositories at global, European, and national levels (e.g. OERCommons, Scientix, Schoolbordportaal^{xxxvi}). The STEAM education communities will also be reached at international conferences such as Ecsite Annual Conference (museums and science centres), PCST - Public Communication of Science and Technologies 2018 conference (scholars and practitioners in the science communication), Eucu.net conferences (the network of children universities) and participation in Scientix Networking events. CCHub partners (1-UL, 2-TCD) run training courses for science communicators, museums staff, scientists and other people involved in science communication activities (for example JCOM Masterclasses^{xxxvii} and masters programmes in Science Communication^{xxxviii}), and will disseminate project results through these programmes in the years to come. CCHub will also use existing mailing lists for this target audience (such as PSCI-COM^{xxxix} and International Network on Public Communication of Science and Technology^{xl}). For this target group, main assets are: the CCHub model, the CCHub Toolkits, the Digital Platform, CCHub MOOC and other educational resources, CCHub evaluation/research results. To effectively communicate these relevant assets, the CCHub project will send newsletters, deliver presentations, distribute, through presentations of CCHub methodologies and results.

CCHub partners and network: Collaborations, partnerships and exchanges (through regular videoconferences will be promoted across the CCHub partners and network. For this target group, main assets are: the CCHub model, the CCHub Toolkits, the CCHub Digital Platform, CCHub educational resources, CCHub events and activities, CCHub MOOC, CCHub social enterprise projects, CCHub sustainability plans, CCHub evaluation/research results, to inform policy and school governance.

Media: CCHub will connect with media networks on an international, European, national/regional and local level. Through press releases for relevant events and invitations to local CCHub events. In addition, consortium partners will leverage their media networks to disseminate CCHub press releases. For this target group, main assets are: the CCHub approach, CCHub events and activities, CCHub youth enterprises, and the CCHub Digital Platform through updates, announcements and press releases.

Table 2.2 Examples of dissemination networks which CCHub will exploit.

Dissemination Network	Nodes	Relevant purpose of network	Use in CCHub	Lead
Ecsite	375	Science centres, museums, science communications professionals	Disseminate project results at the conference (1000 professionals) and Spokes magazine (4000 professionals).	P2-TCD
Scientix	30	Teachers, researchers, project managers in science education, policy makers	Disseminate information and resources in Scientix newsletter and repository, participate in Scientix events.	P2-TCD
Ashoka Fellows	3000	Leading Social Entrepreneurs in 85 countries	Engage network to promote the use of CCHub resources and output.	P5-AHS
Changemaker Schools	200	Ashoka-supported global schools network	Engage network to promote the use of CCHub resources and output.	P5-AHS
Ashoka YouthVenture	6000	Young changemakers in 23 countries	Engage network of youth to promote use of CCHub resources.	P5-AHS
Changemaker XChange	200	Young innovators in 55 countries	Engage network of youth to promote use of CCHub resources.	P5-AHS
Impact Hub network	86	Impact Hubs with 15,000+ members around the world	Dissemination to promote use of CCHub resources.	P3-IH-IT
Universe Awareness	62	Teachers, science educators	Engage network in 65 countries to promote CCHub resources.	P1-UL
ESERO	10	ESA’s European Space Education Resource Office	The ESERO network will disseminate the CCHub resources and output.	P1-UL

TEMI	11	STEM teachers and science educators	Exploit the teachers networks to promote use of CCHub resources.	P1-UL
Europlanet	33	Researchers in planetary science.	Leverage network of researchers to promote engagement with CCHubs.	P1-UL
PCST	2000	Science communications professionals, researchers, writers, web designers	Disseminate methodologies and results to the international community of science communication.	P2-TCD
EUCU.NET	83	The international network of children universities	Dissemination of methodologies and results.	P1-UL
IAU	12 393	Professional astronomers in 98 countries	Leverage network of researchers to promote engagement with CCHubs.	P1-UL
EPS	42	42 physics societies in Europe.	Leverage network of researchers to promote engagement with CCHubs.	P1-UL
European Academies (ALLEA)	59	59 academies in over 40 countries and in diverse scientific fields	Leverage network of researchers to promote engagement with CCHub activities.	P1-UL

Vehicles for creating CCHub impact

The activities will be rolled out through the key channels of consortium partners and dissemination nodes shown in Table 2.3. The estimated reach is based on the relevant figures provided by consortium partners and on previous projects. Special emphasis will be put on social media, which has produced a new shift in educational and pedagogical thinking in the last decade. Information shared as available and openly at one's fingertip shows the need and interest in open education. For a better engagement with students, teachers and beyond, the project will implement a social learning experience through key social media networks to disseminate content and network. To grow this network, CCHub will use the existing social media networks of the project partners which consist of 10 active Facebook pages in total with a fan base of about 200 000 followers, 10 active Twitter accounts with more than 100 000 followers and >500,000 estimated reach. The social network will not only focus on disseminating content, but also to listen to the audience (youth and educators) and engage accordingly.

Table 2.3. Vehicles for creating impact

Channel	Description	Estimated reach
CCHub and Partner websites	Website will be available in 10 languages. Updates posted weekly. Announcements will be shared on partner websites. Estimated reach based on analytics from previous projects and partner websites.	1 000 000
Social media	Channels to engage with the respective target audiences include Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat and Youtube. CCHub will investigate youth trends and use channels that are relevant at time of implementation.	500 000

Newsletters	CCHub will distribute monthly newsletters between M6-M35, and when appropriate, local versions will be distributed as well. Updates and relevant information will be included in the relevant partners newsletters.	50 000
Events	400 activities for youth groups and communities, including co-creation workshops; Participation in relevant national and EU conferences, and other community events. Teacher training events, community engagement and lobbying activities in all CCHub countries.	10 000
Media (including TV, Press, bloggers)	At least 4 press releases during the project (M3: project announced, M13: start pilots, M24: Project highlights. M36: Final projects outcomes). Press releases distributed online and through Press Information of partner organisations. Media will be invited to all key CCHub activities.	1 000 000 engagements
Key Opinion (Digital) Leaders	CCHub will engage with relevant opinion leaders and influencers, e.g. local and global bloggers, vloggers, podcasters and Youtubers (Young people with thousands of views) to maximise the reach of the project.	250 000 engagements

In summary, based on the data from our consortium's previous projects the expected number of young people, educators and teachers and wider society to be reached by CCHub communication initiatives over 3 years is more than 2.5 million individuals

3. Implementation

3.1. Work plan – Work packages and Deliverables

Co-Creation Hub implementation combines a set of specific tasks and components necessary for achieving the strategic objectives set in Section 1 with the skills, competencies and networks provided by the consortium partners. To reach all described aims and objectives of the 36-month Co-Creation Hub project, an integrated project plan and overall work plan strategy of structured work packages and strategic positioned milestones will be applied as described below and in the next section. This research and innovation project is designed is divided into work packages with sublevels of each WP linked to one or more deliverables and to the labour person-months needed for completion. We have flexible partners that have multiple and complementary competencies; our flexible consortium can react well to any problems arising from the interconnection of WPs. In the unlikely scenario of a partner leaving, we can redistribute their work tasks among the other partners.

The project will implement a number of actions through the consortium, in collaboration with local stakeholders to ensure broad involvement of European stakeholders from all relevant levels in the project, and to ensure broad dissemination of the project results. The project outcomes will have extensive impacts across all EU member states and beyond through the well-established research, education, entrepreneurship and innovation community networks of the consortium partners. CCHub will leverage these connections to encourage stakeholder participation and wide participation and engagement within and beyond the EU. The choice of consortium partners from fields such as research, education and academia, private sector (SMEs), STEAM public engagement, and the non-profit sector (NGOs/NPOs) reflects our interdisciplinary approach and broader project outcomes.

For the development of specific components of the CCHub project (e.g., our websites), the consortium will make use of the innovative methodologies like the Scrum framework that emphasizes iterative and incremental agile development. Scrum defines a flexible project development strategy where a development team works as a unit to reach a common goal. It will enable the consortium to self-organize by encouraging close online collaboration (e.g., Slack) with an ongoing flow of information and regular updates concerning the progress (e.g., Basecamp). The work package structure can be found in Table 3.1 and detailed work package content is detailed in the WP description tables (Tables 3.1a). Figure 3.1a provides an overview of the interdependencies among the different Work Packages.

Table 3.1. Work Package Structure.

	Work Package Title	Par. Number	Participant Name
WP1	MANAGE: Project Management and Coordination.	1	UL
WP2	EVALUATE: Assess & Monitor effectiveness of the Co-Creation Hub.	2	TCD
WP3	EXPLORE: Benchmark & Develop New Pedagogical Methodologies on Collaborative Social Entrepreneurship & Innovation.	4	GCU
WP4	ENGAGE: Stakeholder Engagement for Social Change in the the Community through Local Action.	2	TCD

WP5	EMPOWER: Educators and community leaders through online resources and Training Module for broader and wider impact & Scale-up the project.	3	IH-IT
WP6	DISSEMINATE: Project communication, policy exploitation and legacy.	1	UL

Fig 3.1a. Overview of CCHub work packages and their main concepts and components. All the CCHub work packages will feed into the CCHub "on the ground" impacts and in the long-term into the project legacy.

Implementation Timeline

Phase I: Initiation: The project will benchmark and develop pedagogical methodologies in the relevant topics: collaborative social entrepreneurship and innovation with disadvantaged youth (WP3). Project partners and leaders from participating communities and schools^{xli} will participate in the CCHub Kick-off Workshop to co-create the Community Pilots, and will receive training on key topics such as social innovation, tinkering and making, gender equity, and business model development. During the workshop, these explored topics will be co-developed into a one-year *Social Innovation for Youth* pilot, to be implemented with a number of different youth communities^{xlii}.

Phase II: Local Action: CCHub will provide an array of social innovation activities and training for the participants during the pilot phase, as well as an open source platform for resource-challenged communities. A year-long pilot programme^{xliii} will be implemented with young people in participating youth communities and schools in 9 countries. The pilot will begin with co-creation workshops to identify key community challenges^{xliv} around which to develop social enterprises. Young people will be connected with local enterprises and experts in the chosen topic, and will receive training workshops on key social innovation and entrepreneurship skills^{xlv}.

Phase III: Broadening Impact: The pilots throughout Europe will be evaluated through WP2, and the results and case-studies will be collected and published on the CCHub Platform (WP5 & WP6). This Platform will include co-creation guides, localization guides, educational activities, and professional development guides for educators to train young people in key skills and support the creation and implementation of social innovation across Europe. As part of the platform, CCHub will offer a Massive Open Online Course on "Social Innovation for Youth" based on the actions and pedagogical guidelines developed by the project after evaluation of the pilot process (including how to teach social innovation through a variety of formats and timescales and to different audiences). The reach of this course is extensive—hundreds of schools. The Platform will also include a section containing academic research that will inform policy and practice for education for responsible citizenship, to ensure sustainability and serve the largest number of young innovators.

Table 3.1a. Work packages descriptions

Work package number	1			Lead beneficiary							UL	
Work package title	MANAGE: Project Management and Coordination.											
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	
	UL	TCD	IH-IT	GCU	ASH	AE	MB	SI	IH-RO	IH-HU	IH-GR	
Person months per participant:	6	4	4	4	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
Start month	1			End month 36								

Objectives

Co-ordinate the activities and maintain an efficient relationship between the project partners, stakeholders and the European Commission. In particular this Work Package (in collaboration with WP2) intends to achieve the highest standards of quality in the deliverables, and to do so on time and within budget. The specific objectives are:

- Set up the management infrastructure of the project
- Manage the project overall to achieve the project objectives and the requirements of the call
- Ensure the implementation of project activities on time and as described in the proposal
- Address potential issues and take corrective actions as necessary

Description of work

The work package is led by Leiden University. All partners participate in the project management, internal communications activities, and the production of deliverables and reports.

Task 1.1. Set up and run the management infrastructure (M1-M36, Lead: UL with inputs from

all other partners)

- Organise and set up internal communication tools and activities: regular consortium meetings, internal work package meetings, communications platforms, documents sharing platform, etc.
- Constitute the project advisory council including youth, schools and enterprise representatives
- Supervise achievements and monitor state of the art evolution of the project, propose evolution of the project accordingly
- Monitor risk and quality of implementation

Task 1.2. Set up and run the project monitoring system (M1-M36, Lead: UL with inputs and participation from all other partners)

- Monitor each work package progress
- Identify and address potential issues, take or propose corrective actions when necessary
- Ensure the submission of all deliverables of the project on time.
- Coordinate the implementation and submission of the project periodic reports.
- Make sure that the project objectives are achieved with sufficient attention on the requirements of the call.
- Liaise and coordinate with European Commission and other relevant European institutions.
- Work closely with the partners of WP: Evaluate leader to ensure that the identified issues in the implementation of the project are tackled accordingly.

Deliverables

D1.1 First periodic report (M12): report on activity implementation after Year 1 of the project.

D1.2 Second periodic report (M24): report on activity implementation after Year 2 of the project.

D1.3 Final periodic report (M36): report on activity implementation after Year 3 of the project.

Work package number	2			Lead beneficiary							TCD
Work package title	EVALUATE: Assess & Monitor effectiveness of the Co-Creation Hub										
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name of participant	UL	TCD	IH-IT	GCU	AHS	AE	MB	SI	IH-RO	IH-HU	IH-GR
Person months per participant:	4	12	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Start month	1			End month 36							

Objectives

The main objective is to assess and monitor effectiveness and impact of the Co-Creation Hub as whole. The specific objectives are:

- To evaluate the results of each of the 1-year pilot schemes implemented in Phase 2 in youth communities.
- To measure the impact of CCHub on scientific interest and scientific literacy.
- To establish shared measurement practices across the consortium, incorporating an equity perspective by developing a set of goals, strategies and metrics which disaggregate the pilot

participants by gender, age, geography, socio-economic status and other factors.

- To carry out an on-going evaluation of the effectiveness of each work package for the duration of the project and ensure that procedures are in place to implement changes if necessary.
- To develop, pilot and validate a range of research instruments (including questionnaires, interviews and focus groups) to enable a high-quality evaluation of the impact of the CCHub on the participants and the local community (Based on European Key Competences for Lifelong Learning).
- Develop a set of tailored indicators linking community building, managing and nurturing with S.M.A.R.T.^{xlvi} impact measurement indicators.
- To provide forums for the CCHub participants to engage in continuous dialogue with the project/local steering committee to contribute feedback and suggestions on direction — thus ensuring the openness, integrity and social validity of the impact evaluation.
- To implement and analyse the findings of the evaluation and produce an open-access baseline dataset to aid knowledge-sharing and future work in this research area.
- To publish the findings of the impact assessment in open access peer-reviewed journals in the field of education and engagement.

Description of work

This work package will assess the impact of CCHubs in local communities to foster improved science education for all citizens. It will evaluate the development of partnerships between schools, local communities and local industry as well as the contribution to a more scientifically interested and literate society and awareness of and interest in scientific careers. The work package will provide ongoing assessment of the CCHub which will be made publicly available to help provide citizens and future researchers with the tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices in this area.

Task List

Task 2.1 Evaluate effectiveness of all work packages (M1-M36, Lead: TCD, inputs from all partners)

- Devise appropriate process evaluation strategy
- Ensure on-going project quality control

Task 2.2 Develop research instruments (M1-M6, Lead: TCD)

- Create quantitative and qualitative evaluation tools
- Pilot and validate all instruments

Task 2.3 Establish feedback forums (M1-M6, Lead: TCD)

- Facilitate dialogue and feedback mechanisms for participants in each country/hub
- Share learnings across countries to encourage best practices

Task 2.4 Implement evaluation and collect data to establish baseline study (M1-M36 Lead: TCD)

- Carry out interviews, focus groups and questionnaires (pre and post involvement in CCHub)
- Make evaluation available as open-access dataset

Task 2.5 Submit publications for peer-review (M30-M36, Lead: TCD)

- Target appropriate journals for publication of findings
- Write, review and submit publications

Task 2.6 Create “Impact Evaluation Toolkit” to equip citizens and future researchers with the tools and skills to make informed decisions and choices in Social Entrepreneurship (M24-M36, Lead: TCD)

- Combine project findings and baseline dataset in accessible toolkit

- Host and promote toolkit at key events/conferences to ensure impact/legacy

<p>Deliverables</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.1 Feedback forums (M9) • D2.2 Research instruments (M12) • D2.3 Baseline study dataset (M14) • D2.4 Interim on project effectiveness (M18) • D2.5 Impact Evaluation Toolkit (M28) • D2.6 Final report on project effectiveness (M36)

Work package number	3			Lead beneficiary							GCU
Work package title	EXPLORE: Benchmark & Develop New Pedagogical Methodologies on Collaborative Social Entrepreneurship & Innovation.										
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name of participant	UL	TCD	IH-IT	GCU	ASH	AE	MB	SI	IH-RO	IH-HU	IH-GR
Person months per participant:	1	2	2	12	9	2	2	2	2	2	2
Start month	1			End month: 36							

<p>Objectives</p> <p>The main aim of WP3 is to benchmark the progress of the project to date, with a view to developing new pedagogical methodologies for collaborative social entrepreneurship and social innovation. It builds upon WP2 by iteratively incorporating both the learning thus far, and, through a rigorous assessment of peer-reviewed scientific literature and grey (policy) literature, the latest scientific knowledge and research on addressing social exclusion (and youth exclusion in particular) through collaborative approaches to social entrepreneurship and social innovation. It is anticipated that this knowledge will then be used to implement the scaling up and rolling out of the project in future WPs. It will deliberately seek to introduce learning from other European-funded projects concerning social entrepreneurship and social innovation (e.g., WILCO, EFESIIS, CRESSI) to examine the current trajectory with respect to social innovation knowledge capacity in Europe, and the most appropriate strategies to address the needs of specific disadvantaged groups.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Objective 3.1: to understand the latest ‘state of the art’ in social entrepreneurship and social innovation for addressing disadvantage - Objective 3.2: to explore the views of practitioners, identifying areas of best practice from WP2 on which to build - Objective 3.3: through integrating scientific knowledge with more praxis-oriented findings, co-develop new knowledge of pedagogical approaches to social entrepreneurship and social innovation for addressing disadvantage and social exclusion. - Objective 3.4: Provide the a high-quality training in all the relevant aspects of the project to all partners and relevant stakeholders involved in working with youth communities and developing innovative training materials.

Description of work

Task 3.1: Undertake scoping review of literature focused on social innovation and social entrepreneurship-led approaches to addressing disadvantage youth communities (peer reviewed and grey literature) (M1-M7, Leader: GCU)

Task 3.2: Undertake in-depth semi-structured interviews with practitioners (n=60) - Focus Groups - with a view to understanding what has worked well so far, what has not worked so well in Phase I, to establishing best practice, and what learning can be applied and carried over into phases II and III.(M6-M14, Leader: GCU)

Task 3.3: Develop and provide training sessions to the members of the consortium and relevant stakeholders during the training session in Phase I and in cooperation with WP4 (M1-M12, Leader: GCU)

Task 3.4: Produce a synthesis of the state of the art of research and the empirical findings into a combined and accessible report geared towards a wide range of audiences (including academics, policy-makers, practitioners and the public). (M14-M28, Leader: GCU)

Deliverables

D3.1: Scoping Review (M7)

D3.2: Training Report (M12)

D3.3 Consolidated report (M27)

Work package number	4			Lead beneficiary							TCD
Work package title	ENGAGE: Stakeholder Engagement for Social Change in the the Community through Local Action.										
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name of participant	UL	TCD	IH-IT	GCU	ASH	AE	MB	SI	IH-RO	IH-HU	IH-GR
Person months per participant:	12	2 4	16	6	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Start month	1			End month							

Objectives

The main aims of WP4 'ENGAGE' are to develop a framework for co-creation that can be applied by all partners (O4.1 - Inception phase), to oversee the effective implementation of this framework within all of the cooperating communities (O4.2 - Local Action phase) and to support the participating youth and schools as they travel through their social innovation journey by building suitable support networks, providing skills training and offering opportunities to promote their results (O4.3 - Local Action phase)

Objective 4.1: To develop a framework for co-creation that can be applied by all partners in local CCHub actions

Objective 4.2: To oversee the effective implementation of this framework within all of the cooperating communities, and the co-creation and development of the social innovation projects by participating youth (**Local Action** phase)

Description of work

Task 4.1 Organise a network kick-off meeting and training modules (with inputs from WP3 and coordinated with T3.3) for the local facilitators from each of the consortium member institutions as well as representatives from their cooperating communities (M1-10, Task Leader - P2-TCD). The attendees have wide-ranging and diverse expertise and experience working with disadvantaged youth, and this range of viewpoints will be shared during breakout sessions, round table discussions and debates. The results of these will feed into the overall co-creation framework for the pilot phase.

Modules will include the following (with further modules to be developed based on the findings of WP3: EXPLORE):

- Co-creation: a practical how-to approach, facilitated by P3: IH-IT
- State of the art in Social Innovation and Entrepreneurship facilitated by P4 - GCU, based on results of research carried out as part of WP3 - EXPLORE.
- Tinkering and maker-based learning, facilitated by experts from the Tinkering EU project.
- Gender Equity and Social Innovation facilitated by expert representatives of the Hypatia project - specifically the working group responsible for the development of the gender theoretical framework for Hypatia, a H2020 project which aims to promote gender equity in formal, informal and non-formal STEM education.
- Hands-on workshops on Design Thinking approaches will be facilitated by partners Science Gallery Dublin (SGD). Since 2011, SGD have offered a university-accredited module called "Idea Translation Lab" in which students explore innovation and entrepreneurship through design thinking. This will be offered as condensed and adapted version of ITL, and will afford the participants the opportunity to learn by doing - working in small groups using a design thinking approach over 2 hours to create simplified products, business ideas or solutions.
- Developing opportunities and formats for public engagement with STEM + Arts (STEAM)
- Social innovation for inclusive societies - P5-ASH will facilitate a training workshop centred on the concept of "Everyone a Changemaker" which underpins the Changemaker Schools network pioneered^{xlvii} by the global Ashoka network of social entrepreneurs.
- Business model development and startup incubation facilitated by P3: IH-IT

Task 4.2 Development and Implementation of a "Co-Creation" framework for the implementation of the "Local Action" phase of the project in communities. (M10-M26 Leader: TCD) and in schools (Leader: ASH). Each partner collaborates with community organisation leaders to develop and host interesting and engaging public-facing co-creation event for young people from the community to engage with the project, to try out maker-based STEAM activities, and to decide on a number of issues that have social and local relevance in a geographical area, or issues that are specifically relevant to the community in question

- Partners to facilitate initial engagement with community, local enterprises and research universities, and higher or further education institutes.
- Mentorship process with community participants from ideation, to prototype to implementation of social innovation projects
- 10 monthly progress events with each community where participants can showcase progress, ask for help and guidance, and work on developing new skills required for next phase of project.
- Final pitching and dissemination events

Deliverables

D4.1: Report on kick-off event, including video documentation of training modules to be used as professional development tools (Report, M7)

D4.2: Framework for co-creation of social innovation projects with youth communities and schools

(Report, M8)
 D4.3: Report/Framework on co-creation workshops and social innovation projects in youth community groups (Report, M27)

Work package number	5			Lead beneficiary							IH-IT
Work package title	EMPOWER: Educators and community leaders through online resources and Training Module for broader and wider impact & Scale-up the project.										
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name of participant	UL	TCD	IH-IT	GCU	ASH	AE	MB	SI	IH-RO	IH_HU	IH-GR
Person months per participant:	12	12	24	4	12	12	12	12	12	12	12
Start month	1			End month 36							

Objectives: The overall aim of “EMPOWER” is the transfer of knowledge and skills on entrepreneurial practices to a variegated pool of unprivileged youth, using the approach and practices tested and performed in WP3 and WP4. The main intention of the WP is to develop a legacy strategy, to embed the practices developed by the project into the local relevant institutions developing by that a sustainability plan and to train partners and share knowledge within the consortium about economic sustainability in line with their institution mission. The capacity building campaign will be achieved with a direct intervention to the final beneficiaries belonging to the unprivileged categories and through a extensive intervention addressed to trainers and professionals. WP5 will equally perform its work through digital tools and by off line facilitation and training practices, via a comprehensive campaign of engagement of the existing education, social and professional networks in the cities and territories touched by the CCHub project. The following specific objectives will be achieved:

1. Transferring knowledge and practices through local entities, hubs and education & training institutions
2. Building capacities among educators, trainers, teachers, mentors, hosts and facilitators
3. Enhance accessibility and adaptability of the existing tools to the characteristics of the different audiences and learning settings
4. Scaffolding / Building the capacity of schools, as institutions, to participate in pan-European and International relevant projects, programmes and networks.

Description of work
 Once that pilot interventions (Phase II and coordinated by WP4) fostering social entrepreneurship and design thinking among unprivileged youth have been completed (M24), performed practices will be consolidated and transformed into an operational and scalable model. For the development of specific components of the CCHub project (e.g., the websites), the consortium will make use of the innovative methodologies like Scrum methodology which emphasizes iterative and incremental agile development. Scrum defines a flexible project development strategy where a development team works as a unit to reach a common goal. It will enable the consortium to self-organize by encouraging close online collaboration (e.g.: Slack)

Tasks
Task 5.1 - Organise meeting on practices (from WP4 to WP5) from pilot to model (M10-M14,

Leader: IH-IT). – CCHub consortium "Empower" meeting devoted to the bridging between WP4 and WP5. Partners involved in Local Action for the Engagement for Social Change in the the Community will cooperate for supporting IH IT on the definition of a toolkit for self empowerment.

Task 5.2 - Creation of Toolkits. (M16-M30, Leader: IH-IT). Based on lessons learned from Phase I and II, and building on the outstanding results of the Erasmus+ project “Yincubate” (yincubate.com), including one of the intellectual outputs which is a toolkit to support youth in self-assessment and creation of sustainable projects and business ideas (available for free download via bit.ly/toolkit_sp), the WP4 experience will be distilled into a toolkit to be used directly by the young people or through the assistance and guide of facilitators and trainers.

Task 5.3 - Develop and implement of training modules and other resources(M18-M36, Leader: IH-IT). Through the Impact Hub Makers tool and an open Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) on Social Entrepreneurship for Youth . The “Makers” website of the Impact hub network is an exchange tool used daily by +1,500 practitioners working in the Impact Hubs, as hosts, facilitators, mentors, and change makers. The Makers’ platform will be updated and developed with a specific focus on socio-economic inclusion for unprivileged youth, according to the CCHub aims. The MOOC will be developed by the Leiden University's MOOC team, which works with the platform Coursera. This task also includes the organisation of teacher continuing professional development workshops in the partner countries.

Task 5.4 - Run the Award U19 Prix (M20-M36, Leader: AE): As part of the successful Ars Electronica Festival Awards, a special participation will be given to projects developed under the CCHub project. More information: <http://www.aec.at/prix/en/kategorien/u19/>. Ars Electronica Festival will be an opportunity to showcase the best case studies from the CCHub project.

Task 5.5 - Develop a Business Plan for the Co Creation Hub project (M28-36, Leader: IH-IT) as part of the long term sustainability and ambition of CCHub, partners will explore the possibility to raise the necessary funds to scale up the CCHub approach, local partners will also explore the possibility of supporting initiatives to establish additional CCHub programmes in their countries.

Deliverables

D.5.1 – CCHub Empower Meeting (M18)

D.5.2 – Empowerment toolkits (M25)

D.5.3 – Comprehensive and training modules including MOOC (M28)

D.5.4 – Webinars series for youth (at least 10 episodes) (M30)

D.5.5 – Award U19 Prix report (M34)

D5.6 – CCHub Business Plan (M36)

Work package number	6			Lead beneficiary							UL
Work package title	DISSEMINATE: Project communication, policy exploitation and legacy.										
Participant number	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Short name of participant	UL	TCD	IH-IT	GCU	ASH	AE	MB	SI	IH-RO	IH-HU	IH-GR
Person months per participant:	12	10	6	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Start month	1			End month 36							

Objectives

The main objective of the WP6: DISSEMINATE is to ensure a correct distribution and uptake of the CCHub resources. The work package will focus on project communication, publications, networking, policy exploitation and legacy. The main objectives are:

1. To develop a communication and dissemination strategy.
2. To create promotional material for dissemination purposes.
3. To provide regular updates of website and social media channels.
4. To conduct advocacy activities that promote Social Entrepreneurship & Innovation at policy levels, including local, regional and national government
5. Distribute resources and outcomes of project through relevant repositories and other networks such as Scientix.
6. To develop a Data Management Plan, especially for data beyond the project.

Description of work

Task List:

Task 6.1 Setting up a communication and dissemination plan including internal communication and a comprehensive advocacy engagement plan. (M1-M6, Leader: UL)

- Identification of stakeholder and target groups
- Developing a target-group oriented communication strategy
- Developing strategy to reach local, regional and national governments with advocacy activities.
- Develop a data management plan that will include project standards, a framework for research and evaluation during the project and a suggested list of approaches that partners may use. The plan will be developed and updated in collaboration with the partners throughout the lifetime of the project.
- Develop and implement a social entrepreneurship and innovation policy engagement strategy. CCHub partners will also lobby to influence policy and practice.

Task 6.2 Develop and disseminate relevant online and offline resources (M1-M36, Leader: UL)

- Developing and launching of a project brand identity and website
- Translate the project website for the use in at least 9 languages
- Provide information to project partners on how to adapt the website for local uses
- Manage the international content of the website in close collaboration with all the partners.
- Developing dissemination material e.g.: posters, flyers, brochures.

Task 6.3 Day-to-day external and internal communication (M1-M36, Leader: UL)

- Implement plans defined by task 6.1.
- Providing tools for internal communication, like Slack, basecamp or other collaborative tools
- Engage through social media and other relevant media for target audiences
- Maintaining the content of the website and the content of the social media channels (with input from all partners). Each month on a rotating schedule, one CCHub community will be asked to curate the CCHub blog, providing at least one entry (in English) written by users of the CCHub and documenting some of the recent activities.

Task 6.4 Participate in Conferences & Events ensuring a broader dissemination of results (M6-M36, Leader: UL)

- Participate & Support the participation of relevant partners in relevant conferences and workshops, with an emphasis on social entrepreneurship.

Deliverables

- D6.1** Communication, dissemination and advocacy strategy (M4)
D6.2 Promotional material (M7)
D6.3 Data & Innovation Management Plan (M10)
D6.4 Final Data & Innovation Management Legacy Plan (M32)

Table 3.1b: List of work packages

Work package No	Work Package Title	Lead Participant No	Lead Participant Short Name	Person-Months	Start Month	End month
1	MANAGE	P1	UL	25	1	36
2	EVALUATE	P2	TCD	43	1	36
3	EXPLORE	P4	GCU	38	1	36
4	ENGAGE	P2	TCD	142	1	36
5	EMPOWER	P3	IH-IT	122	1	36
6	DISSEMINATE	P1	UL	73	1	36

Table 3.1c: List of Deliverables

Deliverable (number)	Deliverable name	WP number	Short name of lead participant	Type	Dissemination level	Delivery date (in months)
1.1	1st periodic report	1	UL	R	Public	M12
1.2	2nd periodic report	1	UL	R	Public	M24
1.3	Final periodic report	1	UL	R	Public	M36
2.1	Feedback forums	2	TCD	DEM	Public	M9
2.2	Research instruments	2	TCD	DEM	Public	M12
2.3	Baseline study dataset	2	TCD	DEM	Public	M14
2.4	Interim on project effectiveness	2	TCD	R	Public	M18
2.5	Impact Evaluation Toolkit	2	TCD	OTHE R	Public	M28
2.6	Final report on project effectiveness	2	TCD	R	Public	M36
3.1	Scoping Review	3	GCU	R	Public	M7
3.2	Training Report	3	GCU	R	Public	M12
3.3	Consolidated report	3	GCU	R	Public	M27
4.1	Report on kick-off event, including video documentation of training modules to be used as professional development tools	4	TCD	R	Public	M7

4.2	Framework for co-creation of social innovation projects	4	TCD	R	Public	M8
4.3	Report / framework on co-creation workshops and social innovation projects in youth community groups	4	TCD	R	Public	M27
5.1	CCHub Empower Meeting	5	IH-IT	OTHE R	Public	M18
5.2	Empowerment toolkits	5	IH-IT	OTHE R	Public	M25
5.3	Comprehensive and training modules including MOOC	5	IH-IT	OTHE R	Public	M28
5.4	Webinars series for youth (at least 10 episodes)	5	IH-IT	DEC	Public	M30
5.5	Award U19 Prix report	5	IH-IT	R	Public	M34
5.6	CCHub Business Plan	5	IH-IT	R	Public	M36
6.1	Communication, dissemination and advocacy strategy	6	UL	R	Public	M4
6.2	Promotional material	6	UL		Public	M7
6.3	Data & Innovation Management Plan	6	UL	R	Public	M10
6.4	Final Data & Innovation Management Legacy Plan	6	UL	R	Public	M32

Figure 3.1b provides a timeline overview for the CCHub project work packages, tasks and deliverables.

TIMELINE

Fig 3.1b. Timeline overview for the CCHub project work packages, tasks and deliverables.

3.2 Management structure and procedures

3.2.1. Organisation structure and decision-making

The structure overview for the CCHub organisation is summarised on Fig. 3.2a.

Fig 3.2a. CCHub organizational chart, the consortium will have open and frequent communication between the different areas of the project.

Project Officer: The Project Officer appointed by the EU for the project is the link between the project and the European Commission. The Project Coordinator will be the contact point for the Project Officer. Any serious issue, risk, or crucial decision for the implementation of the project will be discussed with the Project Officer.

Project Board: Each partner organisation will appoint two representatives for the Project Board (PB): one representative from the partner organisation plus a young person selected by each partner. One representative of the Project Coordinator (P1 - UL) will be the chairperson of the PB. The Project Board will control the good progress of the project and advise the Project Coordinator on the implementation. The Project Board is responsible for the project implementation in their organisation as agreed in the project description. They guarantee the involvement of Project Managers to implement the activities. The project board will virtually meet once every three months.

Advisory Board: CCHub will establish an Advisory Board (AB). The task of the AB will be to both advise the PB on key aspects of the project and safeguard the project objectives. Each AB member will be selected for a special relevant expertise for Social Entrepreneurship and will receive regular project reports from the coordinator. CCHub will appoint a relevant member for each disadvantaged youth group addressed by the programme, as well as experts in relevant theoretical and practical relevant topics (such as innovation, coding, gender issues). It is expected that the AB will have 10-15 members. The appointment of members must be approved by the PB.

Project Manager (P1-UL): The Project Manager (PM), appointed by the coordinator (P1-UL) has the responsibility of achieving project objectives according to the timeline and requirements described in the grant agreement. PM monitors the progress of each work package and makes sure that deadlines and objectives are met. The PM implements regular risk assessment, identifies potential issues, and proposes mitigations and solutions in relation with relevant partners. The PM reports and discusses EU management aspects and potential serious issues with the Project Officer. The PM will attend monthly WP meetings and organise WP leaders meetings every two weeks.

Innovation Manager: The role of the Innovation manager (IM), appointed by the the coordinator (P1-UL) in close consultation with P3-IH-IT and P4-GCU, will be to ensure that innovative approaches are developed and implemented during the project, supervising the innovations processes to ensure they are followed correctly and successful. The IM will liaise with the PM in a regular basis.

Work Package Leaders (Work Package leader organisation: P1-UL, P2-TCD, P3-IH-IT): The day to day management of the project will be implemented by the work package leaders, each responsible for the implementation of the activities described under their work packages (WP) and communication between partners involved in the same WP. The WP leaders ensure the delivery of WP activities on time and according to the objectives described in the grant agreement. They provide guidance and consultancy to the Project Managers when necessary. They monitor the progress and quality of the work package activities, ensure the submission of related deliverables on time, and collect data for the assessment of the activities of the associated WP. WP leaders should raise any issue or failure to achieve objectives to the Project Coordinator. Work package leaders will meet once every two weeks under the initiative of the PC. Each WP leader will organise monthly WP meeting involving all partners involved in their WP activities.

Local Facilitators: The implementation of the project activities locally is managed by the Local Facilitator, appointed by each partner responsible for implementing a pilot programme. The local facilitator (LF) is responsible for managing the implementation of the pilot programmes at local levels. They are responsible for implementing these activities, collect data for assessment and reports, and support the dissemination activities of the project. Local Facilitators will attend the relevant WP meetings once per month.

Internal Communication Channels

All participants in the project will share common tools to ensure a good communications between partners. *Project Management Software:* A project management system will be set up to be used for the day-to-day project communications. Here partners can open a private and secure communication space. The platform allows to start discussions involving different partners, keep tracks of discussions, share a calendar, and important documents.

Main communication tool: Emails about specific issues and relevant for groups of partners will be the regular communications exchange tool. *PB meetings:* The PM organises meetings with the PB every three months.

Advisory Board meetings: The PM organises an Advisory Board meeting every 6 months. *WP Leaders meetings:* The PM will organise WP leaders meetings every two weeks. *WP meetings:* The WP meetings will be organised by WP leaders and involve all partners involved in the activities of the related WP. *CCHub Local Facilitators meeting:* These meetings will be chaired by the PM and will involve the 11 managers and facilitators. The PM will organise WP leaders meetings every two weeks. *Other meetings:* Extra meetings will be organised as necessary with small groups of partners and stakeholders.

Decision Making procedure

Any serious issue or potential risk for the implementation of the project should be raised by local CCHub Project Managers and Work Package leaders to the Project Manager. Any critical decision for the project will be discussed with the Project Board and raised to the Project Officer when necessary. Extraordinary consortium meetings can be organised in case of emergencies.

3.2.2 Data Management

According to the Open Access requirements for Horizon 2020 projects, results produced will be granted open access principally using the free online access green model. CCHub project: a) is built on previous research results (improved quality of results); b) fosters collaboration and avoids duplication of effort (greater efficiency); c) involves citizens and society (improved transparency of the process). WP1 will develop and implement a comprehensive data management plan to assure a current implementation of the principles explained above. The innovation manager will work closely with the project manager in the development and implementation across the consortium. A Final Data Management Plan will be presented on D6.3 Data & Innovation Management Plan in M10.

3.2.3. Milestones

CCHub will use milestones to make regular checks in terms of implementation and expenditure with the European Union, Advisory board and local CCHub management boards. Table 3.2a provides an overview of the planned milestones.

Table 3.2 a: List of milestones

Milestone number	Milestone name	Rel. WP	Due date (in month)	Means of verification
M1.1	Management Structures Established	1	M6	Report with specific names and roles in the different management structures of Phase I
M3.1	CCHub Training Session	3	M12	Programme and outcomes published on the CCHub website: That will mark the completion of Phase I
M4.1	CCHub Local Action Workshops	4	M24	Training materials, report and photographs published on project website, this is a milestone of Phase II
M5.1	CCHub On-line Resources	5	M30	The publication of a variety of online materials, from toolkits to open-source online courses is a milestone of Phase II. This materials will be available on the project website and available in 9 languages.
M6.1	CCHub Website	6	M8	Website release

3.2.4. Risk mitigation

In the following table 3.2b, the consortium estimates the potential risks that could become critical for implementation for the project and addresses them by proposing mitigation measures. This initial risk assessment will be used as a baseline for potential risks that could appear during the implementation of the project. Risk assessment will be performed at every step of the project and managed as to anticipate and minimise potential issues that may arise. Any identified issue that could become critical for the project achievement of its objectives will be raised and discussed with the Project Officer.

Table 3.2b: Critical risks for implementation

Description of Risk Level of likelihood (Low/Medium/High)	WP invol ved	Proposed Risk-Mitigation Measures
Consortium partner withdraws (Medium-Low)	1	If a partner withdraws, a suitable replacement will be found within the consortium, and if necessary, outside the consortium. P4-GSU is a UK legal entity and fully eligible to participate and receive funding in Horizon 2020 actions. If the situation changes within the implementation of the project, the other academic partners (P1 and P2 in collaboration with P5) will fulfill the tasks. P2 will automatically become WP3 leader.
Reduced interest of the target groups in participation in project activities (Low)	All	Co-creation of the project and pilot activities will ensure target groups ownership, ensuring the long-term participation. If interest is reduced, the community will be consulted and appropriate actions will be taken. If necessary, a promotional campaign will advertise CCHub resources.
Poor engagement of enterprises/civil society (Low)	All	Engagement of stakeholder in the research and co-creation throughout project phases will keep this risk to a minimum.
Disputes and conflicts among consortium partners (Low)	All	Effective and professional conflict management involving all conflict parties equally.
Communication problems in the consortium (Low)	All	Good communication rules and support by modern communication technologies (Slack, Basecamp, etc.).
A partner coordinator or manager withdraws or is incapacitated (Medium)	All	Relevant partner finds a replacement within a month. If needed, relevant tasks will be transferred between partners. The Project Board involving representatives of each organisation are responsible for the good involvement of their organisation in the project.
Lack of internal work capacity (Low)	All	Outsourcing workload or coordinating workloads with partners.
Delay in meeting milestone or deliverable (Medium)	All	Efficient project management will keep this risk to minimum by formulating internal timeframes. Coordinator discusses the reasons for failure with the involved partners and reports to the Project Officer. When necessary, adapted corrective actions will be taken.

3.3 Consortium as a whole

The Co-Creation Hub consortium includes 11 partners with complementary skills, expertise and experience to implement the project through innovative processes. The 11 partners are 3 universities, educational and research organisations (P1, P2 and P4); 5 social entrepreneurship SMEs (P5, P7, P8, P9, P10), 2 social

entrepreneurship not-for-profit organisations (P3 and P11) and 1 Arts & innovation Centre (P6). CCHub will be implemented in 9 European Union member states and 1 associated country (Switzerland) and with the cooperation commitment from 21 relevant stakeholders. A complete list is available in Section 4, Tables 4.1b and 4.1c. The lead partner, Leiden University (P1-UL), has over 10 years of experience running large scale STEAM projects at the national, European and global level. Trinity College Dublin (P2-TCD) has extensive experience in running STEAM activities through Science Gallery Dublin and evaluating their impact and effectiveness through the TCD School of Education. Glasgow Caledonian University (P4-GCU) provides proven experience on theoretical/academic research on co-creation, innovation & entrepreneurship. The Impact Hubs (P3-IH-IT, P9-IH-RO, P10-IH-HU and P11-IH-GR) bring solid expertise on best practices in business incubation as well as mentorship and grassroots experience. Ashoka IE (P5-AHS) has broad experience in social entrepreneurship and access to a large international network of social innovators and YoungMakers through the Changemaker schools, YouthVenture and ChangeMakerXchange. MakeBoutique (P7-MB), ARS Electronica (P6-AE) and SCIENCE IN (P8-SI) provide practical, well-grounded experience in design-thinking and maker-learning and broad access to regional, national and European education networks.

3.4 Resources to be committed

CCHub will be implemented with a highly experienced, and well-qualified staff. A summary of the staff’s previous experience and skills is described on Section 4. The summary of the staff effort on each Work Package is in Table 3.4a. The explanation of use of all resources is in Table 3.4b.

Table 3.4a. Summary of staff effort in person-month (PM)

P	WP leader	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	Total PM
		UL	TCD	GCU	TCD	IH-IT	UL	
1	Leiden University	6	4	1	12	12	12	47
2	TCD	4	12	2	24	12	10	64
3	Impact Hub Siracusa	4	3	2	16	24	6	55
4	Glasgow Caledonian University	4	3	12	6	4	3	32
5	Ashoka	1	3	9	12	10	6	41
6	Ars Electronica, AT	1	3	2	12	10	6	34
7	Makeboutique Association, CH	1	3	2	12	10	6	34
8	Science In, CZ	1	3	2	12	10	6	34
9	Impact Hub Bucharest	1	3	2	12	10	6	34
10	Impact Hub Budapest	1	3	2	12	10	6	34
11	Impact Hub Athens	1	3	2	12	10	6	34
							TOTAL	443

Table 3.4b Travel Costs overview per partner.

Travel	Average costs	Partner 1		Partner 2		Partner 3		Partner 4		Partner 5		Partner 6		Partner 7		Partner 8		Partner 9		Partner 10		Partner 11	
		Pers	Cost	Pers	Cost	Pers	Cost																
Consortium Meetings (3 meetings / 1 rep. / partner) in Leiden, NL	750	0	0	3	2250	1	750	3	2250	3	2250	3	2250	3	2250	3	2250	3	2250	3	2250	3	2250
Review meeting	750	2	1500	2	1500	1	750	1	750	1	750	1	750	1	750	1	750	1	750	1	750	1	750
Training Workshop (WP3)	1000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000
Conferences	1200	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400	2	2400
Partners Exchange (to stimulate knowledge exchange)	1000	3	3000	3	3000	3	3000	7	7000	7	7000	1	1000	1	1000	1	1000	1	1000	1	1000	1	1000
Other local meetings (relevant for the CC Hub project)	300	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200	4	1200
TOTAL			11100		13350		11100		16600		16600		10600		10600		10600		10600		10600		10600

Table 3.4c Other Direct costs overview per partner

Other direct costs	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8	P9	P10	P11
Travel Costs	11100	13350	11100	16600	16600	10600	10600	10600	10600	10600	10600
Hardware / Software	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000	3000
Events logistics including materials. (Average 300 EUR per event, for 40 different events)	12000	12000	12000			12000	12000	12000	12000	12000	12000
Video & post production (including MOOC)	50000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000	10000
Website development & localisation	20000	2500	2500			2500	2500	2500	2500	2500	2500
Impact Hub Platforms			50000								
Ars U19 Prix						10000					
Audit	1500	1802									
Print products	1500										
TOTAL	88000	29302	77500	13000	13000	37500	27500	27500	27500	27500	27500

Table 3.4d 'Other direct cost' items justification for all the partners.

P1 - UL	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	13 350	As per table 3.4b, base travel costs associated with CCHub, like consortium meetings, review meetings, exchange visits and training sessions.
Equipment	3 000	Software/hardware: € 3 000, including laptop and software
Other goods and services	85 000	Events logistics including materials. (Average € 300 per event, for 40 different events): € 12 000, Open Web Platform development including support for 9 languages: € 20 000. Development of MOOC on Social Entrepreneurship with Youth: € 50 000, print products: €1 500 and Audit costs € 1 500
Total	97 600	
Subcontracting (Also on Section 4.2)	5 000	Training costs (2-day workshop on EU Tinkering for 30 participants + renting costs for 4-day CCHUB training session at dedicated room in the Museo Nazionale della Scienza e della Tecnologia "Leonardo da Vinci" in Milan, Italy) - as per H2020 General Annexes: Costs of delivering the training (subcontracting, since the training is outsourced)

P2 -TCD	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	12 340	As per table 3.4b, base travel costs associated with CCHub, like consortium meetings, review meetings, exchange visits and training sessions.
Equipment	3 000	Software/hardware: € 3 000, including laptop and software
Other goods and	26 302	Events logistics including materials. (Average 300 EUR per event, for 40 different events): € 12 000, Development of content for the Open Web platform: € 2 500.

services		Development of local video materials for MOOC on Social Entrepreneurship with Youth: € 10 000 and Audit costs € 1 802
Total	42 652	
Subcontracting (Also on Section 4.2)	10 000	Training costs on Gender, training will be provided by the Theoretical Framework development workgroup of the H2020 Hypatia project. - - as per H2020 General Annexes: Costs of delivering the training (subcontracting, since the training is outsourced)

P3 - IH-IT	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	11 100	As per table 3.4b, base travel costs associated with CCHub, like consortium meetings, review meetings, exchange visits and training sessions.
Equipment	3 000	Software/hardware: € 3 000, including laptop and software
Other goods and services	74 500	Events logistics including materials. (Average 300 EUR per event, for 40 different events): € 12 000, Development of content for the Open Web platform: € 2 500. Development of local video materials for MOOC on Social Entrepreneurship with Youth: € 10 000. Further development of Impact Hub platforms (Makers and members): €50 000
Total	88 600	

P4 - GCU & P5 - ASH	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	16 600	As per table 3.4b, base travel costs associated with CCHub, like consortium meetings, review meetings, exchange visits and training sessions.
Equipment	3 000	Software/hardware: € 3 000, including laptop and software
Other goods and services	10 000	Development of local video materials for MOOC on Social Entrepreneurship with Youth: € 10 000
Total	29 600	

P6 - AE	Cost (€)	Justification
Travel	10 600	As per table 3.4b, base travel costs associated with CCHub, like consortium meetings, review meetings, exchange visits and training sessions.
Equipment	3 000	Software/hardware: € 3 000, including laptop and software
Other goods and services	34 500	Events logistics including materials. (Average 300 EUR per event, for 40 different events): € 12 000, Development of content for the Open Web platform: € 2 500. Development of local video materials for MOOC on Social Entrepreneurship with Youth: € 10 000. Costs associated with the U19 Social Innovation Award:€ 10 000
Total	48 100	

P7 - MB , P8 - SI, P9 - IH-RO, P10 - IH-HU, P11 -	Cost (€)	Justification

IH-GR		
Travel	10 600	As per table 3.4b, base travel costs associated with CCHub, like consortium meetings, review meetings, exchange visits and training sessions.
Equipment	3 000	Software/hardware: € 3 000, including laptop and software
Other goods and services	24 500	Events logistics including materials. (Average 300 EUR per event, for 40 different events): € 12 000, Development of content for the Open Web platform: € 2 500. Development of local video materials for MOOC on Social Entrepreneurship with Youth: € 10 000
Total	38 100	

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Endnotes

- ⁱ UN 2011: http://unctad.org/en/docs/ciimem1d9_en.pdf
- ⁱⁱ Gender considerations for CCHub are further elaborated upon in section 1.3.3.
- ⁱⁱⁱ For an overview of the preliminary pilot programme, see Figure 1.3.
- ^{iv} H2020 Societal Challenges include health; clean and efficient energy; smart, green, and integrated transport; and climate action: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/societal-challenges>
- ^v Overview of CCHub partner communities see Section 1.3.2
- ^{vi} <http://genderfutures.org/gender-equality>
- ^{vii} Furlong, Andy. "Chapter 4." Youth Studies an Introduction. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge, 2013. 75.
- ^{viii} Jacobs, Emma (2015). "Review: Generation Jobless? By Peter Vogel". Financial Times.
- ^{ix} http://www.edf-feph.org/Page_Generale.asp?DocID=12534&id=1&langue=EN
- ^x <http://pjp-eu.coe.int/en/web/youth-partnership/youth-and-disabilities#2>
- ^{xi} <http://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupDetailDoc&id=18892&no=1>
- ^{xii} http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Unemployment_statistics#Male_and_female_unemployment_trends
- ^{xiii} <http://genderfutures.org/gender-equality>
- ^{xiv} OECD Reviews of Migrant Education - Closing the Gap for Immigrant Students: Policies, Practice and Performance: <http://www.oecd.org/edu/school/oecdreviewsofmigranteducation-closingthegapforimmigrantstudentspoliciespracticeandperformance.htm>
- ^{xv} <http://www.mipex.eu/integration-migrant-youth-european-society>
- ^{xvi} <https://www.salto-youth.net/rc/inclusion/inclusionresources/inclusiongroups/inclusionrural/InclusionRuralYouth/>
- ^{xvii} <http://www.edumigrom.eu/>
- ^{xviii} <http://www.museoscienza.org/tinkering-eu/download/Tinkering-A-practitioner-guide.pdf>
- ^{xix} <https://www.coursera.org/learn/tinkering>
- ^{xx} http://www.agencybydesign.org/educator_resource/
- ^{xxi} http://ec.europa.eu/education/policy/strategic-framework_en
- ^{xxii} EU, 2016, Entrepreneurship Education at School in Europe: <http://www.highscope.org/Content.asp?ContentId=282>
- ^{xxiii} <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/fpfs/mwikis/eurydice/images/4/45/195EN.pdf>
- ^{xxiv} http://ec.europa.eu/education/policy/strategic-framework_en
- ^{xxv} See Table 4.1b
- ^{xxvi} http://eacea.ec.europa.eu/education/eurydice/documents/the_matic_reports/135EN.pdf
- ^{xxvii} www.scientix.eu, www.oercommons.org, <http://openeducationeuropa.eu/>, www.tes.com, <http://www.informalscience.org/>
- ^{xxviii} <http://www.ecsite.eu/>, <http://www.teachingmysteries.eu/>, <http://www.space-awareness.org/en/>, <http://www.eusea.info/>
- ^{xxix} Mainly through Work Packages 5 and 6.
- ^{xxx} <http://ec.europa.eu/education/policy/strategic-framework/education-technology.htm>
- ^{xxx1} http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf
- ^{xxxii} <http://www.allea.org/Pages/ALL/4/775.bGFuZz1FTkc.html>
- ^{xxxiii} <http://jcom.sissa.it/masterclasses/>
- ^{xxxiv} <https://thesisin3.com/>
- ^{xxxv} [Mcs.sissa.it](https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/science/science-communication-and-society) and <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/science/science-communication-and-society>
- ^{xxxvi} National repository in the Netherlands: <http://www.schoolbordportaal.nl/index.html?>
- ^{xxxvii} <http://jcom.sissa.it/masterclasses/>
- ^{xxxviii} [Mcs.sissa.it](https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/science/science-communication-and-society) and <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/science/science-communication-and-society> and <https://www.tcd.ie/Education/courses/masters/science/>
- ^{xxxix} <https://www.jisemail.ac.uk/cgi-bin/webadmin?A0=PSCI-COM>
- ^{xl} <http://www.pcst.co/discussion>
- ^{xli} List of businesses, business incubators, civil society, community groups, youth groups and schools provided in Table 4.1a.
- ^{xlii} See youth groups in section 1.3.1.
- ^{xliiii} See CCHub Approach in Figure 1.3.
- ^{xliiv} Linked to the EU Grand Societal Challenges
- ^{xlv} For a complete list of social innovation skills and related CCHub activities, see Table 1.2a.
- ^{xlvi} Specific, Measurable, Assignable, Realistic and Time-related
- ^{xlvii} <https://www.ashoka.org/en/program/changemaker-schools>